

UNIVERSITÀ
DI SIENA
1240

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL, POLITICAL AND COGNITIVE SCIENCES

MASTER IN PUBLIC AND CULTURAL DIPLOMACY

Influencer diplomacy: The role of social media influencers in France's public diplomacy in Brazil

Relators

Prof. Francesco Olmastroni

Controrelatrice

Prof. Linda Basile

Thesis by
Yasmin dos Santos Dutra

Academic year 2023/2024

Abstract

This thesis examines the role of social media influencers (SMIs) in digitalized public diplomacy through a study of Paul Cabannes' collaborations with French diplomatic institutions in Brazil, from April to November 2024. Based on concepts such as opinion leaders, relational public diplomacy, and networked communication, the study analyses Cabannes's impact through his humorous and cultural content, serving as a non-state actor and network bridge between France and Brazil. The combination of engagement metrics and sentiment analysis on Instagram and TikTok reveals that SMIs-diplomatic collaborations have led to significantly more active and passive engagement than conventional public diplomacy strategies, especially on Instagram, where the public engaged in more in-depth conversations. Posts themed around culture and humor drew the most positive sentiment, while politically sensitive content triggered criticism, particularly on TikTok. Digitalized public diplomacy strategies can greatly benefit from partnerships with social media influencers, provided they are supported by effective listening, responsive communication, and a clear strategic vision tailored to each platform.

Abbreviations

ATOOUT	France Tourism Development Agency
IG	Instagram
G20	Group of Twenty
G2P	Government-to-public
GRWM	Get ready with me
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NSA	Non-state actors
P2P	Public-to-public
POV	Point of view
PD	Public diplomacy
PR	Public relations
Q&A	Questions & Answers
SMI	Social media influencer
TT	TikTok
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
US	United States of America
USIA	United States Information Agency

Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction	1
1.1 Research goals and significance.....	4
Chapter 2: Literature review	7
2.1 The new public diplomacy.....	8
2.1.1 Social listening in digital diplomacy.....	12
2.1.2 Non-state actors and social networks.....	17
2.1.3 Relationship-building and second-tier initiatives	20
2.2 Opinion leaders, communication dynamics and public opinion in international affairs.....	27
2.2.1 Social media influencers as opinion leaders and celebrities	34
2.2.2 Communication dynamics.....	39
Chapter 3: Methodology	45
3.1 Research approach and selection criteria.....	45
3.2 Data analysis.....	49
3.2.1 Qualitative content analysis.....	50
3.2.2 Sentiment analysis.....	51
3.2.3 Comparative analysis.....	52
Chapter 4: Case study - Paul Cabannes and France’s digital public diplomacy in Brazil	54
4.1 Introduction to Paul Cabannes	54
4.1.1 Cabannes’ role in public diplomacy and engagement with French institutions.....	56
4.2 France’s public diplomacy strategy in Brazil.....	61

4.2.1 Digital diplomacy initiatives.....	62
4.4 Content analysis: Themes and messaging.....	66
4.5 4.4 Engagement metrics and sentiment analysis.....	74
4.5.1 Engagement metrics across posts.....	74
4.5.2 Sentiment analysis.....	76
4.5.2.1 Sentiment analysis - Post #1 – “France vs Brazil”.....	76
4.5.2.2 Sentiment analysis - Post #2 – "After all, it's a beautiful partnership”.....	79
4.5.2.3 Sentiment analysis - Post #3 – "That’s crazy”.....	80
4.5.2.4 Sentiment analysis - Post #4 – "Thank you to @elysee”.....	82
4.5.2.5 Sentiment analysis results.....	86
4.5 Comparative analysis: Instagram vs. TikTok.....	89
Chapter 5: Conclusion.....	94
References.....	102

List of Tables

Table 1 - Characteristics of Traditional and New public diplomacy (Cull, 2009).....	10
Table 2 - Relational public diplomacy framework (Zaharna, 2009)	22
Table 3 – Grunig & Hunt’s four models of public relations	42
Table 4 - Overview of Paul Cabannes’ collaborations with French diplomatic institutions	47
Table 5 - Comment sampling for sentiment analysis of Paul Cabannes’ posts	49
Table 6 - Areas of content analysis.....	50
Table 7 - Sentiment analysis categorization.....	51
Table 8 - Paul Cabannes’s social media followers	55
Table 9 - Social media presence of French diplomatic institutions in Brazil	63
Table 10 - Engagement metrics of French diplomatic institutions on Instagram	65
Table 11 - Results of content analysis.....	66

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Press conference for the “Spend a Night @ Taiwan’s Presidential Office Building” campaign.....	25
Figure 2 - Paul Cabannes creating content	55
Figure 3 - Paul Cabannes with Caroline Putnoki and Érick Jacquin at the General Consulate of France in São Paulo.....	57
Figure 4 - Paul Cabannes at the 2024 French Cinema Varilux Festival.....	58
Figure 5 - Average Engagements of @carolineputnokiocial on Instagram (September 2024 – February 2025).....	59
Figure 6 - French comedian Paul Cabannes and French President Emmanuel Macron discussing croissants in a humorous exchange	60
Figure 7 - Collaborative Post #1 on Instagram.....	68
Figure 8 - Collaborative Post #2 on Instagram.....	70
Figure 9 - Collaborative Post #3 on Instagram.....	71
Figure 10 - Collaborative Post #4 on Instagram.....	73
Figure 11 - Sentiment analysis of Post #1 on Instagram and TikTok.....	76
Figure 12 - Sentiment analysis of Post #2 on Instagram and TikTok.....	79
Figure 13 - Sentiment analysis of Post #3 on Instagram and TikTok.....	81
Figure 14 - Sentiment analysis of Post #4 on Instagram and TikTok.....	83
Figure 15 - Sentiment analysis across all posts on Instagram and TikTok.....	86
Figure 16 - Sentiment across Instagram	90
Figure 17 - Sentiment across TikTok.....	91

Chapter 1: Introduction

The progress of globalization, combined with modern communication technologies, has promoted interactions across the globe, a process that Castells (2009) identifies as the development of a *network society*. This transformation creates a networked system that prioritizes more connections between societies over fixed state-controlled boundaries. This growing interconnectedness has led governments to begin to understand how public opinion impacts their policies and the importance of engaging with foreign audiences and key stakeholders.

In this perspective, public diplomacy activities came forth to manage foreign publics' perception of international actors to promote national policies and create positive global public opinion. The United States began to understand the value of these activities and, since the 20th century, organizations like the United States Information Agency (USIA) started to develop communication strategies aimed at foreign audiences. As Szondi (2009, p. 303) notes: “Influencing foreign public opinion to achieve national goals and advancing and protecting national interest have always been of key importance for any nation.” Similarly, Seib (2016, p. 10) states that “public diplomacy is important because public opinion matters”, highlighting the need for countries to effectively understand and engage foreign audiences.

Communication studies experts have long been fascinated by the study of sentiments and their effects on public relationships. Lazarsfeld et al. (1948) established their position as pioneers by showing that some individuals play a crucial part in forming public sentiments and preferences. The *two-step communication model*, which they developed, described how *opinion leaders* receive information from mainstream media before sharing it with less informed people, therefore acting as intermediaries in the process of forming public opinion. Katz and Lazarsfeld (1955) developed the “rediscovery of people” concept which demonstrated

that personal communication has a greater effect on people than mass media does (Martino, 2018).

In the present digital age, social media influencers (SMIs) are leading figures capable of initiating discussions about local and global matters and thus affecting public opinion. Through their ability to create interaction and connection with their communities, SMIs are developing into relevant actors in digitalized public diplomacy, assisting government communication with foreign audiences.

Scholars now recognize two distinct phases of public diplomacy through their analysis. On the one hand, Melissen (2005) explains that *traditional public diplomacy* operated through state-focused communication, which connects governments with foreign publics through the term "government-to-people" (G2P). On the other hand, *new public diplomacy* differs from traditional approaches by involving multiple non-state entities, including civil society organizations (Eysink, 2005), private sector entities, and opinion-makers, who operate under the "people-to-people" (P2P) model. Snow (2009) noted that public diplomacy has evolved from government-focused communication into an interactive decentralized system, combining state and non-state actors to form public opinions that influence foreign policy preferences.

This transition has been further developed by digital diplomacy, which uses online platforms for real-time engagement, cultural exchanges, and audience participation. The Internet has transformed how countries project soft power and cultivate relationships with foreign publics, increasingly involving non-state actors, such as influencers, in diplomatic processes.

Indeed, the expansion of cyberspaces had an impact on communication, allowing the real-time delivery of information, interaction, and the creation of digital communities. Reed (2009) has recognized this fact, using the term *digital participation* to describe the process by

which individuals and institutions produce and exchange content. This dynamic has led both state and non-state actors to design digital public diplomacy strategies.

For instance, governments employ audience studies and sentiment analysis to assess how populations react to their diplomatic initiatives as they happen. Cull (2019) explains that social media allows public diplomacy practitioners to “listen” to foreign audiences, which allows them to understand message reception and modify their communication approaches. Sentiment analysis (also known as opinion mining) observes public emotions and opinions about different entities, including individuals, organizations, and worldwide events, as defined by Liu (2012). Through this capability governments can measure public sentiment to improve their digital diplomacy strategies based on audience feedback.

In this digital environment, SMIs are turning into key players in public diplomacy. They have proven valuable to governments, cultural institutions and diplomatic missions by supporting the development of communities, global dialogue and engagement. The digital nature of their work makes influencers more approachable and trustworthy to their followers compared to traditional diplomatic representatives.

This thesis examines how France engages with Brazilian audiences through social media influencers as a part of its public diplomacy efforts. For this purpose, Brazil represents an excellent case study due to its high levels of social media usage and its status as the fifth-largest online market (Statista, 2025). Moreover, 81% of Internet users in Brazil are active on social media (Statista, 2023), allowing influencers to play an important contribution in public opinion and making Brazil an ideal context for analysing digital diplomacy initiatives.

As for France, cultural diplomacy has been a primary method through which the country has interacted with Brazilian audiences, relying on social media influencers to strengthen cultural and political ties between the two countries. In this respect, this study aims to investigate these influencer collaborations by addressing the following research questions: i)

how influencers function as non-state actors in digital diplomacy; ii) which strategies France employs to engage with the Brazilian public through social media; iii) how these collaborations are consistent with public diplomacy theories such as Zaharna's (2009) relational approach and Grunig and Hunt's (1984) two-way symmetrical communication model.

This research studies influencer diplomacy through the lens of public diplomacy by analysing how networked actors affect international perceptions while digital platforms function as diplomatic tools in today's interconnected world.

1.1 Research goals and significance

As international communication increasingly turns towards digital platforms, more and more governments are using social media and digital actors to enhance their public diplomacy efforts. Traditional state-to-state diplomacy has been complemented by non-state actors such as SMIs, cultural organisations and the private sector, thus defining a new model of international relations (Zaharna, 2009; Cull, 2019). In the context of digital public diplomacy, influencers have emerged as cultural intermediaries, promoting cultural relations and interacting with foreign audiences in a more authentic and direct way than governmental representatives.

This thesis explores how France relies on social media influencers to engage Brazilian audiences as a part of its public diplomacy efforts. In particular, the study focuses on the role of SMIs as non-state actors in public diplomacy, analysing how their partnerships with embassies, consulates, and cultural institutions may impact public opinion about France and foster engagement with the Brazilian community. In doing this, I will explore how France incorporates SMIs in its public diplomacy strategies in Brazil and evaluate the extent to which SMIs function as non-state agents in digital public diplomacy. Themes, narratives and messaging strategies employed in these collaborations will be examined to determine how these partnerships align with public diplomacy perspectives, particularly Zaharna's (2009) relational approach, emphasizing long-term engagement, and Grunig and Hunt's (1984) two-

way symmetrical communication model, advocating for mutual dialogue over one-way persuasion. Finally, the impact of audience engagement will be investigated through sentiment analysis to assess how effective SMIs-diplomatic partnerships are in promoting positive public reactions in public diplomacy.

By exploring these dimensions, the research aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on digital diplomacy and investigate how networked influence impacts public diplomacy practices. Moreover, it offers practical insights for policymakers, diplomatic institutions, and scholars interested in the impact of networked influence in contemporary international relations.

For policymakers and diplomatic institutions, the study provides a structured analysis of how foreign governments use social media influencers within their public diplomacy strategies. It highlights best practices and identifies possible risks associated with influencer partnerships for digital engagement, while also evaluating the effectiveness of digital public diplomacy efforts by examining audience perception and engagement.

For academics and researchers, the study expands the existing literature on public diplomacy and digital communication by integrating classical approaches (Cull, 2009; Melissen, 2005) with new networked mechanisms (Zaharna, 2009; Grunig & Hunt, 1984). It analyses the contributions of non-state actors in forming international discourses, offering an understanding of influencer diplomacy as a form of soft power. In addition, it explores Brazil's highly engaged digital cyberspaces, showing how public diplomacy works in one of the most socially connected societies.

Finally, for cultural institutions, embassies and consulates, the study reveals how collaborations with influencers can enhance cross-cultural communication and strengthen diplomatic relations. It demonstrates how foreign public diplomacy can use a country's digital environment to promote cultural exchange and dialogue through social media platforms. By

bridging academic research and real-world implementation, this study contributes to the understating of digital diplomacy strategies and offers practical and theoretical observations on how public diplomacy is being transformed by influencer partnerships in the contemporary world.

Chapter 2: Literature review

Despite extensive research in the field, scholars still debate the exact definition and scope of public diplomacy. The term gained official status with Edward Gullion's 1965 definition, which was motivated by a need to distinguish it from the term propaganda due to negative associations. While some scholars find that public diplomacy is primarily state-driven (Melissen, 2005; Huijgh, 2016), others highlight the growing influence of non-state actors in creating international narratives (Snow, 2009; Lee & Ayhan, 2015).

This chapter analyses the evolution of public diplomacy from its initial form centred in government-to-public (G2P) communication into the network-based approach called “new public diplomacy” (Cull, 2009; Snow, 2020). The turn toward interactive communication models became possible due to technological progress and new media platforms' increasing power (Bjola, 2016; Castells, 2009). Through the "new public diplomacy" framework organizations can establish new ways to connect with publics through social listening and implementing digital diplomacy approaches.

In this respect, this chapter depends on key theoretical frameworks which explain public diplomacy and international communication by emphasizing listening as essential for relationship-building in diplomacy (Cull, 2019); the increasing influence of non-state actors, such as NGOs, civil society and social media influencers on diplomatic strategies (Lee & Ayhan, 2015; Danzek, 2023); and the intersection between public diplomacy and public relations, particularly in digital communication strategies (Grunig & Hunt, 1984; Szondi, 2009).

This thesis will focus on how opinion leaders form public opinions through their influential effect. Lazarsfeld's two-step flow model and its application in digital spaces (Lazarsfeld et al., 1948; Martino, 2018), will support the study of influencer diplomacy in France-Brazil relations. Social media influencers function as public diplomacy intermediaries

in integrated media environments by strengthening state messages while reaching foreign audiences through new communication channels (Danzek, 2023).

Finally, the chapter explores digital diplomacy through state use of social media platforms and influencer partnerships to boost soft power (Nye, 2004) and engagement with foreign publics. The analysis presented in this chapter establishes a theoretical framework to understand digital public diplomacy in contemporary international relations.

2.1 The new public diplomacy

Among the various means a country can employ in order to control its image abroad and interact with foreign publics, public diplomacy has been considered one of the most effective. However, the development of public diplomacy has been affected by the ongoing debate concerning the terminology of the field. The term was made popular in the United States (US) when Edward Gullion, then dean of the Fletcher School of Law and Diplomacy at Tufts University, established the Edward R. Murrow Center of Public Diplomacy in 1965 (Cull, 2020). Gullion's idea of public diplomacy laid the foundation for its academic and practical development:

Public diplomacy [...] deals with the influence of public attitudes on the formation and execution of foreign policies. It encompasses dimensions of international relations beyond traditional diplomacy; the cultivation by governments of public opinion in other countries; the interaction of private groups and interests in one country with another; the reporting of foreign affairs and its impact on policy; communication between those whose job is communication, as diplomats and foreign correspondents; and the process of intercultural communications (as cited in Cull, 2020, p. 13).

The term "public diplomacy" replaced propaganda as the preferred diplomatic practice after Gullion made it official. The United States Information Agency (USIA) played a great

part in his decision to adopt the new term because they sought to eliminate negative associations with propaganda (Cull, 2020). The implementation of public diplomacy served two purposes: it transformed how people viewed USIA activities and simultaneously enhanced the professional standing of its employees by changing their public image from “vulgar” public relations agents to diplomats (Cull, 2020, p. 15).

A key difference between propaganda and public diplomacy is the role of listening. Melissen (2005, p. 22) emphasizes this notion, stating that public diplomacy “listens to what people have to say” rather than simply trying to persuade opinions. Cull (2019, p.1) reinforces this view: “Propaganda is about dictating your message to an audience and persuading them you are right. Public diplomacy is about listening to the other side and working to develop a relationship of mutual understanding”.

Similarly, Huijgh (2016, p. 437-438) describes public diplomacy as the “diplomatic communication between political entities and people” and “the practice of states’ one-way communication with foreign publics”. This perspective highlights public diplomacy’s focus on foreign publics, therefore differentiating it from traditional diplomacy done solely among diplomats. However, by defining it as a “one-way communication process”, Huijgh (2016) pictures foreign audiences as mere targets – passive participants in the communication process – similar to Cull (2019)’s understanding of propaganda.

In contrast, new public diplomacy does not regard foreign audiences as passive receivers, seeking to inform them without meaningful efforts to promote dialogue or encourage active participation. Listening, in fact, is recognized as one of the most important elements of new public diplomacy and one of Cull (2019)’s five strategies for engaging foreign publics as an international actor: *listening; advocacy; cultural diplomacy; exchange diplomacy; and news/international broadcasting.*

Cull (2019, p. 4) defines listening as “an actor’s attempt to manage the international environment by collecting and analysing data about international publics and using that data to redirect its policy or its communication accordingly”. However, he advises that listening must not only gather information to superficially satisfy public opinion. To be truly effective, listening must be both active and systematic for a long-term impact (Cull, 2019).

Snow (2020) further supports the importance of relationships and trust-building in public diplomacy, arguing that: “an ongoing emphasis on relationships with publics is still our best predictor of actual future behaviour. It changes the focus in public diplomacy from a reactive stance to a proactive stance” (Snow, 2020, p. 11). This shift, as mentioned by Snow (2020), aligns with the wider evolution from traditional public diplomacy (G2P – government-to-public) to new public diplomacy (P2P – people-to-people). Traditional public diplomacy mainly aims to influence foreign publics by disseminating information. As Snow (2009, p. 7) observes, “conventional public diplomacy emphasizes citizens but has at times emphasized citizens in asymmetrical one-way efforts to inform and build a case for a nation’s position”. This approach, however, does not include the essential element of listening. Snow (2009, p. 7) warns: “traditional public diplomacy tends to take the public for granted, or views public opinion measurement as a necessary evil in foreign policy”.

On another hand, new public diplomacy recognizes the growing influence of both state and non-state actors (NSAs) in impacting foreign policy strategies (Snow, 2009). In other words, it acknowledges that non-governmental institutions, private actors, and civil society play an active part in diplomatic dynamics. Cull (2009) also outlines these developments in his report *Public Diplomacy: Lessons from the Past*, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 - Characteristics of Traditional and New public diplomacy (Cull, 2009)

Dominant characteristics	Traditional public diplomacy	New public diplomacy
Identity of international actor	State	State and non-state

Tech. environment	Short wave radio Print newspapers Land-line telephones	Satellite, Internet, real-time news, mobile telephones
Media environment	Clear line between domestic and international news sphere	Blurring of domestic and international news sphere
Source of approach	Outgrowth of political advocacy & propaganda theory	Outgrowth of corporate branding and network theory
Terminology	“International image” “Prestige”	“Soft power” “Nation brand”
Structure of role	Top down, actor to foreign peoples	Horizontal, facilitated by actor
Nature of role	Targeted messaging	Relationship-building
Overall aim	The management of the international environment	The management of the international environment

Note. Data adapted from Cull (2009).

From this comparison between G2P and P2P public diplomacy models, three key lessons emerge for this study. First, public diplomacy should pay much attention to listening and real conversation. Informing foreign publics is essential, but it should not be the sole focus. To avoid reverting to traditional public diplomacy’s one-way communication model, international actors must implement active listening practices, fostering reciprocal relationships (Cull 2009). Second, non-state actors (NSAs) are increasingly involved in contemporary public diplomacy. It is important to understand their impact in order to develop appropriate, participatory public diplomacy strategies. Third, relationship-building is the key to successful public diplomacy. Long-term relationships with foreign publics are also important to sustain engagement and trust (Zaharna 2009).

In the following subchapters, we will analyse each of these three focal points of new public diplomacy – listening, non-state actors, and relationship-building practices - in the context of digital diplomacy practices, including the use of social media and cooperation between SMIs and state actors.

2.1.1 Social listening in digital diplomacy

As part of the new public diplomacy model, Snow (2009, p. 6) stresses the advent of “user-friendly communication technologies” and the increase of “people-to-people exchanges, both virtual and personal, across national borders.” Within this context, Cull (2019, p. 37) highlights the revolutionary potential of social media sites that have “opened undreamed-of possibilities in listening,”

In his work *Real-Time Diplomacy*, Seib (2012) raises a concern about how policymakers can interpret the rise of individual expression online as “dangerous” and might struggle to incorporate social media into their processes. However, he also emphasizes social media and its interactive nature as a powerful tool for listening, considering “time is long past when one-way pronouncements rather than balanced conversation could suffice” (p. 108). This viewpoint acknowledges that adapting to the world of social media can be challenging for governments, as they were used to retaining more control over the narratives about their countries and policies.

The idea that social media can empower individuals and contribute to a more networked reality is reinforced by Babla (n.d.) in a blog article for the Center on Public Diplomacy. She highlights how social media provides a platform for voices that were traditionally excluded or overlooked in diplomatic discourse. She emphasizes that: “If good public diplomacy begins with listening, then practitioners must turn an ear to these online spaces” (Babla, n.d., p. n.d.). This perspective reinforces the idea that digital platforms are affecting the way public diplomacy operates, requiring state actors to engage with diverse voices beyond traditional diplomatic channels.

Before the development of digital tools, public diplomats assessed public opinion through opinion polls, open-source media studies, and both formal and informal conversations

with diplomats and civilians (Cull, 2019, p. 4). In addition to these strategies, Cull (2019) explains that:

Social media have made it possible to deploy a host of real-time listening tools to track responses to a piece of public diplomacy from retweets for messages on Twitter to detailed real-time analytics of the responses to a speech, both positive and negative (p. 26).

Beyond simply tracking engagement, Cull (2019) highlights that social media enable data mining and public opinion analysis, allowing actors to develop deeper insights into their audiences. Di Martino (2020) builds on this idea, arguing that social media not only helps refine ongoing public diplomacy efforts but also plays an advisory part in influencing future policies by raising awareness among state actors. He explains: “A public diplomat who is aware of the opinions shared in an online conversation will be more likely to engage with users since (s)he can promptly respond to critics and suggestions on social media” (Di Martino, 2020, p. 133).

Storie and Marschlich (2023) further support this belief by listing ways in which governments can take advantage of monitoring social media:

First, a mix of qualitative and quantitative measurements can be used to explore public opinion and attitudes, which can be done through sentiment analysis. Second, public diplomacy actors can explore how messages travel in their networks and whether they have any influence over the discussions in the networks. Third, public diplomacy actors can use hashtag correlations to understand if there is a relationship between different issues discussed in a country (p. 27).

Among the advantages outlined by Storie and Marschlich (2023), conducting sentiment analysis on social media is a well-known practice for public diplomats. A practical example of how sentiment analysis can be applied to assess public perception is the 2020 study *Evaluating Online Public Sentiments towards China*, which examined public sentiment toward China on

Twitter during the 2019 Chinese National Day. Conducted by Tsinghua University's researchers Xu Yekai, He Qingqian, and Ni Shiguang, the study collected over 300,000 tweets in Chinese and English (249,602 in English and 5,150 in Chinese). Using a hybrid sentiment analysis method combining Support Vector Machine (SVM) and a dictionary-based approach, this methodology achieved an impressive accuracy rate of over 96%.

Xu's and colleagues' goal was to understand how sentiment patterns aligned with the official National Day celebrations, revealing noteworthy differences between English and Chinese tweets, as well as variations across different countries. These sentiment trends appeared to correspond with the official diplomatic relations each country maintains with China: "English tweets as a whole were more negative towards China, and countries that enjoy relatively better relationship with China tend to hold a more positive view..." (Xu et al., 2020, p. 14).

Another recent example comes from the Swedish Institute, operating under the Swedish Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA). Since 2016, Grundel and Stenberg (2019) have been monitoring discussions about Sweden across social media channels and other digital platforms, in four different languages (English, Spanish, Russian, and Arabic). Their research demonstrates how public diplomats can leverage social listening to track long-term trends, follow real-time conversations, and identify key communicative opportunities:

Not only do we follow everything that is published about Sweden, but also everything that is published about, for instance, sustainability, innovation, gender equality, and migration in relation to discussions about Sweden. If someone posts something about 'climate change' or 'green energy' and Sweden is mentioned in that same post, our digital tool registers this as being part of a larger discussion about sustainability and Sweden. It is important to keep in mind that individual posts do not necessarily matter

– *but when larger chunks of data are collected, it is possible to register patterns and trends for a specific topic* (Grundel & Stenberg, 2019, p. n.d.).

This way of using social listening is more specific and can help the government of Sweden navigate through the global conversations more efficiently. Furthermore, these tools enable the Swedish Institute to find out how large facts – for example, political statements or international events – influence the public discourse in Sweden. For instance, when the Swedish musician Avicii passed away, the authors observed a sudden increase in the discussions. By tracking these conversations, they were able to learn about the public’s reaction and could use this information in designing effective social media campaigns as they state: “In some cases, the Swedish Institute has used these findings to create digital communication projects of our own” (Grundel & Stenberg, 2019, p. n.d.).

Grundel & Stenberg (2019) also conducted sentiment analysis, by identifying “whether the posts are positive, negative, or neutral in tone based on what words and sentences are used in the post.” This method, although seemingly simple, can help governments determine perceptions of their foreign publics regarding a particular strategy or the country itself.

The results from these two different studies – conducted by state (Swedish Institute) and non-state (researchers from Tsinghua University) actors – demonstrate that social media platforms can serve as powerful tools for capturing opinions and sentiments from foreign publics regarding a policy, event, or even a government itself. Whether through large-scale sentiment analysis or real-time engagement with foreign publics, social listening allows state and non-state actors to respond strategically to emerging narratives.

Building on this discussion, the *Key Influencers in Public Diplomacy 2.0: A Country-Based Social Network Analysis* study examines the role of digital interaction between nations and foreign audiences within the framework of Public Diplomacy 2.0. Ingenhoff, Calamai, and Sevin (2021) identified key influencers on X (formerly Twitter) and assessed their impact on

influencing a country's image. This study specifically explored the influence of key individuals (though not necessarily SMIs) in how their audiences engaged with content related to a given country, unlike the previous two studies which focused on overall sentiment analysis.

Using a two-month dataset of tweets, researchers collected 12,455 posts mentioning Switzerland, Austria, and the Netherlands, identifying 288 influential users who contributed 848 tweets. Through *social network analysis* and *content analysis*, the study applied centrality measures – degree centrality, betweenness centrality, and closeness centrality – to determine influence levels and assess their impact on country branding (Ingenhoff, Calamai, & Sevin, 2021).

Ingenhoff, Calamai, and Sevin (2021)'s research categorized tweets under the four dimensions of country image created by Buhmann and Ingenhoff (2015b): *functional* (economic and political aspects), *normative* (values and ethics), *aesthetic* (tourism and culture), and *emotional* (sentiments toward the country). Their findings revealed that the aesthetic dimension dominated discussions on Switzerland and Austria, particularly around topics like tourism and travel, while the functional dimension was more prominent in the Netherlands, emphasizing innovation and economic competitiveness.

One of the study's key conclusions is that "for all three countries, the most active users were individual accounts, which were both more active and were more engaged with by other users" (Ingenhoff, Calamai, & Sevin, 2021, p. 9). In other words, individual users, rather than official government accounts, were the most influential in affecting a country's image on the social network X (Twitter), representing half of the identified influencers. Meanwhile, governmental and intergovernmental organizations, NGOs, and politicians constituted a smaller proportion of influencers.

However, the study acknowledges certain limitations, such as language constraints (as only English hashtags were analysed) and a focus on message dissemination rather than

measuring behavioural or attitudinal changes in audiences: “While we argue that social media chatter in itself should be monitored, further studies are also needed to analyse the impact of such chatter on audiences” (Ingenhoff, Calamai, & Sevin, 2021, p. 9). Despite these limitations, the research demonstrates how social media communication campaigns can influence perceptions of a country and suggests that its methodology could be integrated into public diplomacy measurement tools for assessing the effectiveness of country branding on digital platforms.

Public diplomacy in the digital era is no longer about simply broadcasting messages but about actively interpreting and adapting to global conversations. As we move forward, the integration of these listening tools with other aspects of new public diplomacy – such as partnerships with non-state actors – further highlights the evolving nature of diplomatic communication in a networked world.

2.1.2 Non-state actors and social networks

Lee and Ayhan (2015) state that public diplomacy was first used to distinguish this form of diplomacy from the traditional one and include publics in the core of the practice. Public diplomacy has recently been called *new public diplomacy* due to socio-political changes and technological advancements that have instigated changes to the practice. This has led to the expansion of the field to include non-state actors such as NGOs, civil society, and individuals in contributing to the formation of international perceptions and relationships.

According to Lee and Ayhan (2015), only some actions of non-state actors have been taken into account when examining public diplomacy goals; still, these actors can significantly contribute to the achievement of diplomacy objectives. Lee and Ayhan (2015) describe this as an outcome-based approach, where the results of non-state actors’ activities may naturally overlap with state interests: “In which outcomes of activities of an entity overlap with public diplomacy objectives [...]” (Lee & Ayhan, 2015, p. 60). This intersection between state goals

and non-state actors' independent initiatives creates opportunities for collaboration, particularly when shared interests exist: "As potential partners if there are mutual interests" (Lee & Ayhan, 2015, p. 62).

From a strategic point of view, similar partnerships are most valuable for state agencies that may not have much credibility in certain networks or with certain publics. According to Lee & Ayhan (2015), local non-state actors are usually more reputable in the eyes of the public as they are not as limited by the national agenda like government agencies. They explain the advantages of using these actors in these terms:

Emphasizing what public diplomacy can achieve beyond national interests and collaborating with stakeholders to achieve them together can indeed reinforce other public diplomacy objectives in the long run. It is non-state actors who are not trapped in the boundaries of national interests and enjoy more credibility for such activities, as proved in their active advocacy in every area of global public goods from banning landmines to fighting environmental degradation" (Lee & Ayhan, 2015, p. 63).

While Lee & Ayhan (2015) primarily focus on NGOs as non-state actors, their insights can be extended to individuals contributing to public diplomacy. For instance, the authors note that public diplomacy can be most effective when domestic publics and diaspora stakeholders are involved. This is particularly important for this study, which aims to explore how a diaspora stakeholder (Paul Cabannes) acts as an unofficial public diplomat of France in the context Brazil's networked society.

It is worth noting that Lee and Ayhan (2015) identify two key characteristics for successful state engagement with partners: *network density* – the number of actual ties divided by the number of potential ties, where higher density makes it easier to propagate norms, values and shared knowledge; *network centrality* – the level of centrality of an actor in the network that enables the actor to exercise leadership in public diplomacy and develop and maintain

connections, information sharing, and collaboration. These characteristics should be considered when positioning and studying the impact of non-state actors in the context of the new public diplomacy.

One of the most relevant examples of non-state actors who naturally function as network hubs is SMIs. They are able to develop digital communities, which are settings where people come together to watch content, talk to each other, and build relationships based on interests. These digital spaces have their own culture, which is in line with the definition of digital cultures given by Reed (2019, p.2) as “the social relationships that are formed in the world of the Internet, video games, smartphones, and other forms of high technology”. This contradicts the notion of the online audience being a single, undifferentiated mass, depicting them as various digital tribes existing on different spaces

Undoubtedly, social media has played a central part in digital diplomacy campaigns over the last decade, primarily due to its ability to facilitate information-sharing, interaction, and self-expression among users. Each platform not only enables unique forms of media contents – such as text, images, and videos – but also fosters the emergence of distinct digital cultures and communities, as described by Reed (2009). According to Scheule (2024, p. n.d.):

With the proliferation of social media, a new kind of group of people with enormous reach evolved: “content creators”, also called “influencers”, because of their influence on a large audience. In the digital space, influencers hold enormous potential for generating soft power. Unlike royals, who primarily interact with heads of state and political decision-makers, influencers are very close to ordinary people.

The content produced by SMIs varies widely, ranging from humour and personal storytelling to discussions on politics, relationships, and niche interests like gaming, film, and art. Some influencers also use their platforms for educational purposes, sharing knowledge on

mental and physical health, financial literacy, and culinary arts, demonstrating their ability to serve as informal educators and cultural intermediaries within the digital public sphere.

To assess the influence of SMIs within a social network, one key measure is degree centrality, which quantifies the number of connections a user has. In line with what Lee and Ayhan (2015) proposed, degree centrality can be analysed in: i) ‘in-degree centrality’, that is, the number of users who follow a particular node, indicating how influential or widely recognized the user is within the network; ii) and ‘out-degree centrality’, meaning the number of users the node follows, reflecting its level of engagement with others (Bjola, 2016).

The increasing relevance of non-state actors in public diplomacy demonstrates how influence is no longer confined to governments and official institutions. NGOs, civil society groups, and individual content creators contribute to affecting international perceptions, sometimes even unintentionally aligning with diplomatic objectives. This dynamic is particularly evident in digital diplomacy, where SMIs act as cultural intermediaries, bridging the gap between state narratives and online communities.

As this study examines the role of Paul Cabannes, an example of a diaspora influencer, it considers how his digital presence allows him to function as unofficial yet impactful actors in France’s public and cultural diplomacy efforts in Brazil. This evolution from traditional diplomacy to networked diplomacy emphasizes the need for governments to engage with these new players strategically.

2.1.3 Relationship-building and second-tier initiatives

Another distinguishing characteristic of the new public diplomacy is the change from mere propagating information to foreign publics to prioritising relationship building. Melissen (2005, p. xix) characterizes public diplomacy as “the relationship between diplomats and the foreign publics with whom they work”, a definition that correlates with Zaharna’s (2009)

relational dimension of public diplomacy. This approach focuses on the creation of ties between the agents, namely, diplomats and foreign publics, rather than sending messages.

In “Mapping out a Spectrum of Public Diplomacy Initiatives: Information and Relational Communication Frameworks” (2009), Zaharna identifies two different frameworks within public diplomacy: the *informational framework*, based on one-way communication and message reception, and the *relational framework*, based on dialogue, trust, and long-term relationship. She then goes further to illustrate how various public diplomacy practices have evolved towards a more relational and networked approach.

The information framework views communication as “primarily a linear process of transferring information, often with the goal of persuasion or control” (Zaharna, 2009, p. 88). Zaharna classifies activities falling within this framework as heavily focused on the message, highly centralized and controlled by state actors, and offering minimal opportunity for two-way interaction with the public. This type of communication is usually employed in the context of advocating policies or marketing a country and is therefore very purpose-directed (Zaharna, 2009). However, this approach is not without its problems, particularly in terms of credibility, because it may be seen by the public as a propaganda tool of state actors. As Zaharna (2009, p.89) points out:

In today's highly competitive information environment, where political entities must compete for audience attention and message acceptance, credibility is becoming a prime determinant of persuasive value. The more credible the information content or source, the more persuasive value it has.

On the other hand, Zaharna (2009) brings forward the relational framework as another way of looking at public diplomacy. As the name suggests, relationships are at the core of this framework and public diplomacy efforts are aimed at developing and sustaining real bonds. The strategies in this framework focus on; identifying mutual interests between policymakers

and publics; facilitating direct, interpersonal communication; coordinating rather than controlling the initiative; valuing participation over presentation by utilizing interactive communication channels; emphasizing continuity and sustainability over short-term efforts.

Zaharna (2009) identifies a growing trend among scholars and practitioners toward adopting a relational framework for public diplomacy. However, she refutes the idea that effective relationship-building strategies can mainly be achieved through cultural programs. Furthermore, she highlights the broader potential of relational initiatives beyond the traditional focus on cultural and educational exchange programs often emphasized in U.S. public diplomacy.

In her thorough investigation of the relationship-building strategies in public diplomacy, Zaharna (2009) has distinguished the potential of initiatives into three levels (Table 2): the first tier (exchange programs and visits), the second tier (partnership coordination), and the third tier (policy networking and coalition building). She classifies these initiatives according to the level of participation with the public, time frame, type of coordination, public diplomacy skills employed, and their relation to the policy objective.

Table 2 - Relational public diplomacy framework (Zaharna, 2009)

Tiers	Examples of initiatives	Participation level	Time frame	Coordination	Public diplomacy skills	Policy objective
First tier	Exchange programs	Individual	Short-term (days, weeks)	Limited	Basic coordination and Individual-level interactions	Primarily non-political
	Visits					
Second tier	Cultural and language institutes	Institutions, communities, societies	Open-ended	Shared	Interpersonal communication, sustained contact, cultural sensitivity,	Mixed (political and non-political)
	Development aid projects					

	Twinning arrangements				relationship nurturing	
	Relationship-building campaigns					
	Non-political networking schemes					
Third tier	Policy networking strategies	Countries, non-state actors	Long-term	Negotiated	Facilitation, coordination, advocacy, negotiation, mediation	Highly political
	Coalition building					

Note. Data adapted from Zaharna (2009).

In her assessment, Zaharna (2009) also raises a concern of understanding communication as the same as information and recommends a more balanced use of both informational and relational frameworks, as one complements the other rather than being mutually exclusive. In other words, while relational aspects of public diplomacy are becoming increasingly essential, informational activities still hold value, particularly when strategically combined to enhance the effectiveness of public diplomacy efforts.

For the purpose of this research, Zaharna's (2009) second-tier initiatives in public diplomacy require further focus for the categorization of state actors' partnerships with SMIs on digital platforms. These second-tier initiatives are particularly important because they are usually open-ended and can be either short- or long-term goals. In addition, they are characterized by the shared coordination of partners, a combination of political and nonpolitical policy objectives, and high cultural sensitivity and relationship management.

Moreover, it is important to explore Zaharna's other contributions to public diplomacy, including her study on network purpose and design. By correlating networks as structures and collaborations as processes, Zaharna (2014) explains that, as social media facilitates network-building in public diplomacy, these types of initiatives are becoming increasingly common nowadays. As for collaborative efforts, Zaharna (2014, p. 173) observes that they are less

frequent, as “individuals are not only connecting and sharing information, but through the process of their interactions are generating knowledge, innovation, and synergistic results.”

When considering “key participants” in networked public diplomacy efforts, Zaharna (2014) underlines two groups based on their goals: policy-oriented and nonpolitical initiatives. While the first focuses on pursuing political objectives, seeking to change opinions or push for certain policies, the nonpolitical efforts: “may engage stakeholders on issues such as science, medicine, education, or the environment and seek goals such as mutual understanding, relationship building, or collaborative exchanges” (Zaharna, 2014, p. 176).

Similarly to Lee and Ayhan, Zaharna (2014) also discusses the concepts of network density and centrality, outlining advantages and disadvantages of denser networks. Actors in denser networks are well-connected, interacting more often and sharing ideas more easily, which helps spread the same values and behaviours. On the other hand, this excessive proximity can limit the exchange of new ideas, as Zaharna (2014, p. 179) states that “sparser networks also exhibit less redundancy, and can be comparatively more efficient than the dense network.”

As for network centrality, it relates to how the network is governed, if it is centralized in one or more focal points, or rather decentralized. Zaharna (2014, p. 181) explains: “The optimal degree of centralization depends on the purpose of the initiative. Centralization may be beneficial when focused on simple tasks, but less effective for complex tasks.” As we will explore the contributions of SMIs in the context of networked public diplomacy, the definition of centrality can be examined from the level of government control over SMI-driven initiatives.

Additionally, Zaharna (2014, p. 181) highlights the influence of *network bridges*, which she describes as “often a person on the periphery of a network, serves as a conduit for information and resources and can facilitate external relationship building on behalf of the network.” Furthermore, she stresses how beneficial these bridges can be to promote

relationship-building in public diplomacy strategies. In the empirical section of this thesis, we will examine how SMIs could be considered as bridges between their digital communities and diplomatic institutions, working to facilitate relationships within this networked environment.

These partnerships between state agencies and non-state actors, who can be perceived as network bridges, can be initiated when a network realizes that their goals align, even unintentionally. Lee and Ayhan (2015) support this idea, explaining this unintentional policy convergence is possible and can contribute to achieving general diplomatic objectives.

A good example of a partnership between SMIs and governments, especially diaspora influencers living outside their home countries, is the 2023 Taiwanese campaign “Spend a Night @ Taiwan’s Presidential Office Building”. According to Su (2024), the program brought international influencers to stay at the Presidential Office in Taiwan and produce content about the country.

Figure 1 - Press conference for the “Spend a Night @ Taiwan’s Presidential Office Building” campaign.

Note. Image credit: 總統府 / Flickr. (2023, April 21). 「2023 來去總統府住一晚」免費體驗活動報名正式啟動記者會 [Photograph]. Flickr. <https://www.flickr.com/xyz> (CC BY 2.0).

This campaign, which was carried out by several government agencies, was a soft power project, which was meant to change the image of Taiwan and make it more friendly and open to the world. The campaign's logo as an open door was also meant to symbolize the same message of openness and an invitation to the world. There were 10 groups from 11 countries in 2019 and 15 groups from 13 countries in 2023, and all of them were influencers. Some of the well-known influencers who were part of the project include Nuseir Yassin and Alyne Tamir (Nas Daily) as well as Mitchell Moffit and Gregory Brown (ASAP Science), who created Taiwan-focused content as part of the initiative (Su, 2024).

Given the increasing emphasis on relational public diplomacy, second-tier initiatives and networked initiatives (i.e., collaborations with non-state actors) can provide states with an effective way to develop long-term relationships with foreign publics. Unlike short-term informational campaigns, these partnerships are based on real, continuous contact, understanding of mutual interests, and cultural compatibility, which are less prone to changes in political orientation. Social influencers, especially those with international following, are a new category of actors in these initiatives, helping to build diplomatic narratives through their trustworthiness.

Through Cabannes' case in engaging Brazilian audiences in French public diplomacy, this study aims to show how their contributions fit in Zaharna's (2009) relational framework of trust and shared communication as opposed to one-way communication. Thus, for the modern public diplomacy, it is crucial to understand second-tier initiatives and networked initiatives as digital diplomacy develops.

2.2 Opinion leaders, communication dynamics, and public opinion in international affairs

In the book chapter “Rethinking public diplomacy” (*Routledge Handbook of Public Diplomacy*), Snow (2009) highlights the impact of technology in promoting increased public involvement in foreign relations. This change led to the understanding of public opinion as an essential aspect of the policymaking process. Manor (2019, p. 12) reinforces this viewpoint, correlating the development of new public diplomacy strategies to the rise of a new media landscape, “characterized by continuous flows of information within and between networks of connected individuals.”

Although Web 2.0 is what often comes to mind when discussing technology, it is important to mention the two major revolutions in communications and transport that occurred in the 20th century. These, together with the advancement in trade and finance, sparked a phenomenon described as a “growing consciousness of a rapidly shrinking world” (Steger, 2003, p. 33). This growing interdependence had a large impact on the interconnectedness between national and international affairs, not only politically and economically, creating a global agenda (Taylor, 2002, p. 70).

Manuel Castells, the originator of the *network society* concept, provides critical insights into the impact of globalization on society and the centrality of international communication technologies within this context. Castells (2009, p. 21) defines networks as “complex structures of communication constructed around a set of goals that simultaneously ensure unity of purpose and flexibility of execution by their adaptability to the operating environment.” He notes that before globalization became the norm, societies were predominantly state-centred, with well-defined boundaries and clear sources of power. Castells (2009, p.19) further explains:

In historical terms, the state (national or otherwise) may have been able to function as a gatekeeper of network interaction, providing some stability for a particular

configuration of overlapping networks of power. Yet, under the conditions of multilayered globalization, the state becomes just a node (however important) of a particular network, the political, institutional, and military network that overlaps with other significant networks in the construction of social practice. [...] However, a more constructive approach to the understanding of the process of historical change is to conceptualize a new form of society, the network society, made up of specific configurations of global, national, and local networks in a multidimensional space of social interaction.

Castells (2009) argues that while globalization itself is not a new phenomenon, the advent of modern communication technologies served as a catalyst that drove it to record levels in the 20th century. He explains:

[...] the forces driving globalization could only be effectuated because they have at their disposal the global networking capacity provided by digital communication technologies and information systems, including computerized, long-haul, fast, transportation networks [...]. This is, in fact, what separates, in size, speed, and complexity, the current process of globalization from previous forms of globalization in earlier historical periods. (Castells, 2009, p. 24-25)

Cronin (2013, p. 25) agrees with this view by crediting the emergence of new communication technologies – such as the telegraph, telephone, radio, and television – as a foundation for great societal changes. According to the author, these technologies transformed the course of human conflicts by introducing new opportunities for a state “to govern, to mobilize, and to prosecute and win wars” (Cronin, 2013, p. 25). Cronin’s observation assumes that, as access to new information technologies advanced throughout society, expanding their reach to the public, the more potential to exert influence they held. Like globalization, the

concern over what the masses thought of their governments' policies was not a modern phenomenon. As Hucker (2020, p.10) recollects:

Even prior to the twentieth century, political, intellectual, technological, and cultural shifts had combined to reveal to the public the power and influence that they wielded. [...] If “news” had been important from the days of ancient Greece, through the Roman Empire and into the medieval era and beyond, it assumed an unprecedented significance toward the end of the early modern period.

While Hucker (2020) explains that, historically, nation-states were mostly concerned with the influence they held within their territorial boundaries, Taylor (2002) reinforces that this concern did not include diplomacy and international affairs, which were regarded as “the sport of kings” and the public opinion of the masses received limited attention (Taylor, 2002, p. 59). However, as Hucker (2020) notes, the rise of emerging media channels significantly changed this dynamic, promoting activities like polling and public relations (PR) as governments and corporations increasingly monitored public opinion. The author observes:

New media (most notably radio, but also cinema and, soon enough, television) provided new mechanisms for reflecting, assessing, and also shaping the mood of the listening and watching public. Public relations also grew in prominence, prompted by both commercial imperatives and the apparent ability of Europe’s dictators to shape and mold a pliable public opinion in their image. The polling industry grew exponentially after the Second World War, while television steadily began to eclipse radio and even the printed press as the dominant medium through which the public garnered information about world events. (Hucker, 2020, p. 5)

Given the growing importance of understanding public opinion, scholars such as Harold Lasswell¹ and Walter Lippmann² became prominent names interested in examining the implications of mass communication, public opinion, and propaganda strategies in international affairs. As Hucker (2020, p. 13) observes, in 1927, Lippmann criticized the public as ‘inexpert’, ‘intermittent’, easily distracted, and only interested in foreign affairs during dramatic conflicts. He argued that public opinion was unreliable to support governments, leading to ‘failure or tyranny’ when directly influencing diplomacy.

Hucker (2020) further highlights that Lippmann’s analysis of public opinion as unreliable and easily manipulated gained wider acceptance after World War II, mostly due to “recent examples of dictatorships directing and manipulating their own publics to support the most insidious objectives” (Hucker, 2020, p. 14). Taylor (2002) supports this view, adding:

[...] there remained a feeling within foreign policy-making elites that diplomacy was too serious a business to be left at the mercy of institutions that pandered to commercial rather than national interests (i.e. newspapers). Walter Lippmann’s seminal 1922 study, Public Opinion, reinforced this assumption, not least because it argued that the press was doing such a poor job in preparing the public sufficiently for them to share in informed policymaking.

Hucker (2020) argues that the concept of public opinion has been historically overlooked by international historians. Even if public opinion was frequently mentioned, it was rarely defined with precision, being assumed to represent nothing more than “a manifestation

¹ Harold Lasswell (1902–1978) was an influential American political scientist and communication theorist known for his studies on propaganda, public opinion, and media influence. He developed the famous communication model: “Who says what, in which channel, to whom, and with what effect?”

² Walter Lippmann (1889–1974) was an American journalist, media critic, and political commentator. He is known for his book *Public Opinion* (1922), in which he discussed the role of the media in shaping public perceptions and introduced the concept of “the manufacture of consent.”

of a general will” (Hucker, 2020, p. 3). To prevent repeating the same mistake in this study, before examining the historical attempts by communicators and diplomats to manage public opinion, it is essential to first explore its definition and its impact on the policymaking process.

Firstly, it is important to question who is the so-called “public” in this equation. For David L. Weakliem in his book *Public Opinion* (2020), social classes play a big part in its definition. For most of human history, ordinary people did not have sufficient access to information and education, as well as time, to dedicate the necessary attention to public affairs. With the social and economic changes caused by the Industrial Revolution, a middle class began to develop throughout societies and “more people became aware of the government and acquired more means to influence it” (Weakliem, 2020, p. 3). From then to our current times, Weakliem (2020) argues much has changed, where now the “public” is understood as the “entire adult population, and people have become accustomed to offering opinions on all kinds of topics” (p. 3).

Similarly, Taylor (2002) argues that the more people had access to information, the more policymakers in democratic states were forced to take accountability and recognize a social role of serving the public. The recognition of taking an informational proactive stance “gave rise to ever-increasing state-sponsored media activity – press relations, information departments and the like – in an attempt to ensure that official versions of events prevailed over possible privatised media speculation” (Taylor, 2002, p. 61).

This perspective correlates with Hucker’s (2020, p. 166) statement that “the only public opinion that matters as a diplomatic actor is that which is perceived to exist by those who formulate policy”. In other words, public opinion mostly reflects the views that policymakers acknowledge as influential or relevant. Castells (2009, p. 28) further supports this idea through his exploration of the concept of value, which he describes as “an expression of power”. Castells (2009, p.28) argues that “whoever holds power (often different from whoever is in

government) decides what is valuable”, emphasizing the dynamics between power and public perception in managing public opinion.

Furthermore, Hucker (2020) identifies two contrasting views on public opinion: one representing it as an irrational, emotional crowd, and the other viewing the public as “an enlightened diplomatic actor” (Hucker, 2020, p. 168). A good example of dismissing the public as ignorant and unqualified for active participation in public affairs comes from a U.S. State Department official, cited by Bernard Cohen³ (1973, p. 72): “To hell with public opinion [...] We should lead and not follow” (as cited in Hucker, 2020, p. 15). In the end, what truly seems to matter is the policymakers’ perception of whose opinions carry influence and, consequently, power.

A clear example is reflected when governments seek support and validation from their own citizens to implement military efforts. In this sense, Olmastroni (2014, p. 206) explains governments often resort to framing strategies to win domestic support, such as “to formulate persuasive messages to convince people of the soundness of their position.” Moreover, Olmastroni (2014, p. 72) further argues that:

Since a military operation is more likely to be approved if it is described as a legitimate response to an armed attack and because international authorisation and domestic support are two important conditions to the use of force, a government could seek to create consensus either by fabricating or portraying a danger as an ‘existential and imminent threat’ to the state.

Similarly, Perla (2011) highlights the significant impact domestic public support has on the success of military policies abroad, with public sentiment acting as a critical factor. His study observed how military actions, and the use of force are sensitive topics in view of how

³ Bernard Cohen (1926–2024) was a political scientist who, in 1963, highlighted the media’s agenda-setting role, stating that the press tells people “what to think about”, not necessarily “what to think”.

passionately people tend to react to them – on one side, some citizens judge them as violent and unhuman acts that should be deterred and discouraged, while on another, government’s supporters perceive them as necessary acts toward a greater good (Perla, 2011, p. 147). For example, during the 1980s, public opposition to U.S. intervention in Nicaragua restricted President Reagan’s policy, as extensive criticism led Congress to limit funding for the Contra forces, effectively restricting further escalation (Perla, 2011, p. 145).

The exploration of a government’s pursuit of domestic support, such as the contributions of sentiment-based opinion-making, aligns with Castells’ (2009) exploration of political cognition and the role of emotion in information processing. Depicting on studies by Marcus et al. (2000), MacKuen et al. (2007), Neuman et al. (2007), and Marcus (2008), Castells (2009) emphasizes that emotional applications and rational decision-making are complementary, with their interaction and influence depending on the context of the decision-making process (p. 146). Castells (2009, p. 148) explains:

Emotion influences political judgment via two paths: (a) loyalty to parties, candidates, or opinion-leaders based on an attachment to these leaders (when circumstances are familiar); (b) critical examination of parties, candidates, or opinion-leaders based on rational calculations influenced by heightened anxiety (when circumstances are unfamiliar). In both cases, rationality alone does not determine decision-making; it is a second-level processing of information that depends on activated emotions.

Within this framework, the impact of mainstream media becomes crucial. As the primary source of political information for the general public (Perla, 2011), media outlets hold significant power to influence public perceptions through their framing of government policies. Moreover, Baum and Potter (2015, p. 32) discuss how leaders in contemporary democracies who rely on media channels to address their citizens become more constrained, as their actions are constantly subject to evaluation. Baum and Potter (2015, p. 32) further elaborate that:

The extent of public access to reliable political information via the media ought therefore to influence leaders' willingness to pursue potentially risky foreign policy actions. After all, absent access to the media, citizens will lack sufficient credible information to evaluate a leader's foreign policy performance, at least in the short run (that is, until the longer-term consequences are apparent).

The enduring impact of public opinion on international relations and policymaking becomes evident when examining its historical significance. Throughout the 20th century, this diplomatic transformation created new strategies for policymakers to manage their communication with publics due to the increased importance of global public opinion. Castells (2009, p. 53) emphasizes this dynamic:

Because the public mind – that is, the set of values and frames that have broad exposure in society – is ultimately what influences individual and collective behavior, programming the communication networks is the decisive source of cultural materials that feed the programmed goals of any other network. Furthermore, because communication networks connect the local with the global, the codes diffused in these networks have a global reach.

The digital age led to new patterns in public opinion formation and mobilization, according to Castells (2009) and Perla (2011). As social media has made opinion leaders and influencers relevant actors in creating new narratives, public diplomacy analysis requires an understanding of these dynamics to comprehend the changing media environment.

2.2.1 Social media influencers as opinion leaders and celebrities

For many years, the formation and expression of public opinion and the means of mass communication have been the subject of analysis. With the development of communication

technologies and changes in the socio-economic sphere, scholars such as Lazarsfeld et al. (1948) were among the first to attempt to systematically understand these questions. The first to introduce the concept of the two-step flow of communication was their foundational study *The People's Choice*, which suggested that *opinion leaders* function as intermediaries between the mass media and the public, interpreting and explaining media messages and then passing them on to their contacts. This was a challenge to the prevailing doctrine that positioned the mass media as directly affecting the individual (Lazarsfeld et al., 1948).

In Martino's (2018) reflection on the impact of *The People's Choice*, the concepts of opinion leader, personal influence, and two-step flow communication continue to be relevant in the social media context. He emphasizes that Lazarsfeld et al.'s work was a turning point in communication research by incorporating social psychology and group dynamics into mass communication studies, which led to other studies and criticisms. As the two-step flow model of communication has been criticized for being too simplistic, Martino (2018) believes that the existence of digital influencers shows opinion leadership in a contemporary way, confirming how relevant these early theories still are in discussions on digital communication and public opinion. He states that:

The idea of "digital influencers", that is, people who, via social networks, "influence" or "lead trends" could be understood as a distant offspring of the "opinion leader" originally understood by the authors of "The People's Choice" as a highly specialized person in some subject that others turn to when they need to make a decision (Martino, 2018, p. 6).

As a result, classifying SMIs as the new opinion leaders implies differentiating between them and conventional celebrities. While celebrity fame is often attained by conventional celebrities through institutional gatekeepers such as television, film, and major media,

influencers produce content and engage directly with their audiences to create their celebrity capital (Carrillat & Ilicic, 2019). Their impact is mainly determined by their dialogue with their followers who, according to (Khamis et al., 2017), are the gatekeepers that determine who is credible and who is not in the digital networks.

A critical factor in this ‘celebrification process’ is content traversal, which refers to the sharing of influencer-generated contents across various digital platforms and audience marketplaces (Abidin, 2018). Through their multi-platform strategy, influencers solidify their star status and are, therefore, valuable actors to brands, organizations, and even governments (Carrillat & Ilicic, 2019). This ease in transition between the platforms helps them to reach out to more people, gain their trust and, therefore, tell the narrative that the public diplomacy agencies should tell (Abidin, 2021).

This change in influence is especially significant in public diplomacy, where states are now partnering with influencers to reach foreign audiences. Although classic celebrity diplomacy can be linked to people like Audrey Hepburn, Princess Diana, or Bono, who employed their public status to promote humanitarian and diplomatic goals (Cooper, 2008), the appearance of digital influencers has opened up new opportunities for interaction.

In his analysis of Cooper’s (2008) findings, Kellner (2010) notes that celebrity status can be a useful asset in diplomacy if combined with media spectacle and people’s engagement. He explores how Barack Obama played his celebrity status during his presidential campaign and diplomacy, thereafter, harnessing traditional media, the Internet, and social media to engage with people around the world. His political activism interspersed with cultural visibility made the United States, and especially African Americans, more appealing to the international community, according to Kellner (2010).

Similarly to Danzek’s (2023) understanding of influencer diplomacy, defining the application of non-state social media actors to promote policies, ideas, and affect public

opinion, this practice of diplomacy by influencers fits well with the rise of social media platforms. However, she points out that these ideas are not always consistent with the state diplomacy objectives because influencers work outside of the government's control. This offers both advantages and disadvantages for public diplomacy, most particularly for democracies desiring to broaden their impact abroad without sacrificing legitimacy or turning into propaganda machines (Danzek, 2023).

Danzek (2023) explains how influencers can build momentum for stories, alter the perception, and moderate foreign policy debates, while providing instances, including the coverage of Alexey Navalny's poisoning, which was shared on social media and received international coverage, and the discussion on President Duterte's drug war, in which online campaigns defined the local and international outlook. The War in Ukraine has also demonstrated the potential of influencer diplomacy. Ukrainian soldiers have been posting Telegram and TikTok videos of day-to-day life, destruction, and military operations, influencing global opinion and NATO's part in the conflict. On the other hand, pro-Kremlin influencers and the Wagner Group have used social media to propagate propaganda and impact public opinion (Danzek, 2023).

In this highly digitalized environment, diplomats can also learn from influencer strategies to make conventional public diplomacy campaigns more personal and therefore more compelling and effective. The governments can also adopt the influencer-style content like the shots of daily diplomatic life, cultural interactions, or work with NGOs and local organizations. Some foreign ministries, as Danzek (2023) observes, have started sending influencers to cover cultural events and produce natural content that will be interesting for their followers, not promoting the state-sponsored propaganda.

Furthermore, Danzek (2023) suggests that adopting some of the most popular social media trends, such as 'Get Ready With Me' (GRWM) or 'Point of View' (POV) videos may

also assist diplomats in revealing their everyday lives and thus making the diplomatic service more understandable to the people. Thus, the concept of influencer diplomacy can be considered as a successful attempt to modernize traditional public diplomacy practices with the help of informal leaders: social media influencers who can attract the target audiences with their posts and comments (Danzek, 2023).

This section has outlined how social media influencers function as the modern opinion leaders, celebrity endorsers, and diplomatic intermediaries. The two-step flow model of communication is still relevant in the current world as SMI acts as a mediator between mass media and the public (Martino, 2018). Their ‘celebrification process’, content traversal, and engagement-driven influence are different from traditional celebrities (Carrillat & Illicic, 2019).

Still, the line between the traditional media personalities and social media influencers continues to fade as the use of digital communication increases. Celebrities have always been utilized in diplomacy through their humanitarian activities and power diplomacy. However, social media influencers represent a new way of engagement. The difference is that while traditional celebrities rely on the media to construct their celebrity status, influencers gain credibility from their audience.

This makes them quite useful in diplomatic processes that entail trust, understanding, and the participation of the target audience. In this study, which aims to reveal how influencers function as the modern opinion leaders, we discuss the consequences of their contributions in diplomatic communication. SMIs’s potential to create public stories, influence politics, and work with state institutions indicates a change in the way that public diplomacy operates in the digital environment.

2.2.2 Communication dynamics

Moving forward on to the realm of digital diplomacy, Manor (2019, p. 14) debates the use of the term, as it regards it as almost a separate category under public diplomacy practices. He therefore suggests the use of the term “digitalized public diplomacy” as preferred to the describe the process of incorporating digital tools into diplomatic activities.

The rise of digital diplomacy (or perhaps the more suited term *digitalized public diplomacy*) has transformed the way states engage with foreign audiences, leveraging online platforms to foster dialogue and influence international narratives. Social movements such as #MeToo and #BlackLivesMatter exemplify how digital spaces facilitate global engagement, allowing both state and non-state actors to influence public discourse (Snow, 2020). However, alongside these opportunities, digital diplomacy has also been met with challenges, particularly the spread of disinformation and fake news, which threaten a state’s credibility. As Snow (2020, p. 8) points out: “Fewer than a third of Americans believe that government officials are credible. There is little faith in information that leads to the truth since two-thirds of those polled can no longer distinguish between real and fake news”.

This credibility surpasses the U.S. and affects all countries utilizing digital platforms for public diplomacy, highlighting the need for strategies that increase trust and engagement with foreign audiences (Snow, 2020). Given this landscape, states are increasingly seeking partnerships with non-state actors to bridge communication gaps, engage international publics, and build credibility in ways that official state channels may struggle to achieve (Danzek, 2023).

This increasingly digital atmosphere challenges diplomatic institutions to adapt and to communicate effectively with their foreign publics. In this sense, Manor (2019) notes a shift from early to more recent stages of digitalized public diplomacy, as public diplomats realized their strategies were regarding digital platforms as one-way message dissemination tools. According to Manor (2019, p. 103):

...the second stage of digitalization saw a shift from targeted to tailored communication in which diplomats crafted content that met the characteristics of specific digital publics including their values, norms, history, needs, interests and usage of digital platforms. This shift is important as tailoring is representative of the internal conflict that accompanies the digitalization of public diplomacy, a conflict between diplomats' desire to create online relationships and diplomats' well-entrenched norm of obtaining influence.

While *tailored communication* initiatives are more considerate of foreign publics, hence increasing the success rates of these initiatives, Manor (2019, p. 130) raises caution, since “tailoring also serves to facilitate the goal of influence”. In other words, state actors must learn to navigate their goal of building meaningful relationships with other actors, both state and non-state, while working towards achieving their policy objectives.

In the pursuit of relationship-building within digitalized public diplomacy, the author emphasizes how other disciplines integrate this relational aspect in their practices. For instance, Manor (2019, p. 130) highlights the field of public relations (PR), which “focuses on creating (and possibly leveraging) relationships with stakeholders”. In fact, PR becomes highly relevant because they provide a framework for managing communication between national institutions and their audiences (Grunig & Hunt, 1984). Just as corporations use PR strategies to influence their brand image and establish trust with consumers, governments are increasingly adopting PR techniques to improve their public diplomacy efforts.

When state actors' partner with SMIs, they are performing relationship management and reputation-building strategies, which are the core of PR (Szondi, 2009). Using the principles of PR, states can improve their trustworthiness through the use of SMIs who have developed a good relationship with their followers. Moreover, they increase their coverage by using digital influencers to reach out to the public that may not otherwise be reachable and

contribute to more productive communication by using influencer-based and audience-oriented approaches rather than depending on conventional top-down communication.

However, the relation between PR and public diplomacy has been an issue of discussion for a long time. According to Floyd (2007), some scholars have stated that public diplomacy is different from PR because diplomacy is the process of developing relations over the years while public diplomacy is marketing. On the other hand, Grunig (2013) has pointed out that public diplomacy and PR are compatible and that public relations can only improve diplomatic processes by increasing the level of engagement and credibility (as cited in Snow, 2009).

Floyd (2007) argues that public diplomacy is not about ‘selling’ a specific policy but about building relationships and fostering dialogue: “Public diplomacy is more about influencing foreign audiences and fostering dialogue between American citizens and institutions and their counterparts abroad than it is about ‘selling’ a specific policy” (Floyd, 2007, p. n.d.).

Similarly, Duffey (1995, as cited in Snow, 2009 p. 10) argues that public diplomacy must surpass public relations techniques, emphasizing its part in connecting with foreign publics through deeper engagement:

Let me just say a word about public diplomacy. It is not public relations. It is not flakking for a Government agency or even flakking for America. It is trying to relate beyond government-to-government relationships the private institutions, the individuals, the long-term contact, the accurate understanding, the full range of perceptions of America to the rest of the world.

While Duffey (1995) and Floyd (2007) position public diplomacy as distinct from PR, other scholars see PR as an essential component of modern diplomacy. Grunig (2013) argues that PR is not simply about ‘selling’ policies but rather about “managing communication

between an organization and its publics”, which is central to both corporate branding and public diplomacy efforts (as cited in Snow, 2008, p. 10).

In the context of state-SMI collaborations, PR becomes particularly relevant because influencers act as mediators between states and foreign publics. This correlates with James E. Grunig and Todd Hunt’s (1984) *Four Models of Public Relations*, which provide a useful framework for understanding how communication strategies evolve within diplomacy (as cited in Golan & Yang, 2014, p. 11).

Table 3 – Grunig & Hunt’s four models of public relations

Model	Characteristics	Communication flow	Goal
Press agency/publicity	One-way communication, focus on persuasion and promotion, often lacks truthfulness.	One-way	Promotion
Public information	One-way communication, focus on accurate and truthful dissemination of information.	One-way	Information
Two-way asymmetrical	Two-way communication, feedback used to persuade, aims to benefit the organization over the public.	Two-way	Persuasion
Two-way symmetrical	Two-way communication, mutual understanding, aims to benefit both organization and publics.	Two-way	Mutual understanding

Note. Data adapted from *Excellence in Public Relations and Communication Management* (1st ed.) by J. Grunig, 2013, Routledge, as cited in Golan & Yang, 2014.

According to Grunig & White (2013, p. 53), the highest PR standard is the two-way symmetrical model, which creates bidirectional understanding between an organization and its publics. This is consistent with the evolution in public diplomacy from one-way communication to relationship marketing strategies. Therefore, it is evident why public relations (PR) techniques are gradually being incorporated into contemporary diplomatic practice (Szondi, 2009, p. 297).

One of the greatest strengths of public diplomacy is its association with power, especially in the sense of how nations attempt to influence foreign audiences to support their

agendas. As Snow (2009, p. 3) points out, “public diplomacy is inevitably tied to power”; thus, it is important for diplomats to have an understanding of various power types, including soft power (Nye, 2004).

In this light, SMIs can be key intermediaries of power, specifically soft power, through which states are able to transmit cultural, social, and political messages in a more tangible and appealing manner. According to Nye (2004, p. 5), soft power is the ability of a country to “shape the preferences of others” through culture, values, and policies. As for the SMIs, due to their high level of trust from their community, their ability to spread the nation’s messages and affect public opinion can be critical in digital diplomacy.

Therefore, when governments partner with influencers, they employ PR-driven diplomatic strategies that help states reach new audiences, promote trust, and enhance their global image. While some scholars argue that PR and public diplomacy are distinct, their increasing overlap in digital spaces demonstrates that PR frameworks offer important insights for understanding modern public diplomacy efforts.

Digital diplomacy is an expanding concept that represents an evolution in how countries manage their communication resources. Interaction, credibility, and narrative are the new pillars of public diplomacy. Manor (2019, p. 45) adds further insight into how these digitalized public diplomacy initiatives can be developed by distinguishing networks from communities:

Networks are goal-oriented, temporary social structures characterized by weak ties. Communities, by contrast, are more permanent structures characterized by strong ties among members, an emotional connection to other members, and continuous engagement with members over long durations of time. Communities generally have something in common, such as religion, values, or sexual orientation.

In other words, Manor (2019) highlights the significance of communities when practicing digitalized public diplomacy, perhaps even more than networks. Hence, this

viewpoint emphasizes the potential of collaborating with SMIs, as they excel at creating and nurturing their own digital communities. Furthermore, as nations work to improve their international image, these partnerships can provide a way of addressing people who might otherwise be difficult to reach.

However, it also raises concerns about credibility and the dangers of associating state agendas with independent content creators. This thesis aims to explore how governments face these challenges when they partner with SMIs in their communication strategies, incorporating insights from public relations models. In the end, realizing the complex relationship between PR, public diplomacy, and soft power offers a richer understanding of how international engagement is evolving in the 21st century.

Chapter 3: Methodology

This chapter outlines the methods employed to investigate how France uses social media influencers to engage Brazilian audiences as part of its public diplomacy strategies. Given the qualitative nature of the study, content analysis was chosen to examine the themes, narratives, and messaging strategies used in these influencer collaborations. Moreover, sentiment analysis of the audience engagement provides insights into public perception and the level of interaction with these initiatives.

Using Zaharna's (2009) relational public diplomacy framework, this study assesses whether these influencer collaborations are aimed at developing long-term engagement and relationships or if they are merely one-way promotional efforts. Furthermore, Grunig and Hunt's (1984) two-way symmetrical model is applied to evaluate whether these partnerships value active dialogue between France's diplomatic institutions and Brazilian audiences or are merely one-way communication tools.

3.1 Research approach and selection criteria

This study utilizes a qualitative content analysis combined with sentiment analysis to investigate how France's public diplomacy targets Brazilian audiences through social media influencers. The research focuses on analysing social media content on Instagram and TikTok, shared by French diplomatic institutions in Brazil in collaboration with the social media influencer Paul Cabannes. In particular, the first part of the research examines diplomatic narratives and how they are framed in the context of influencer collaborations. The second part evaluates the use of engagement strategies to encourage audience participation. Drawing on sentiment analysis, this study explores how audiences perceive and respond to these initiatives.

In evaluating these collaborations, Zaharna's (2009) distinction between informational and relational public diplomacy serves as a theoretical framework. In fact, this study aims to determine whether these initiatives prioritise short-term messaging or long-term cultural engagement. Further, Grunig and Hunt's (1984) two-way symmetrical model is applied to assess whether these efforts foster reciprocal communication or remain primarily state-driven promotional endeavours.

As mentioned in the introduction, Brazil represents a large and socially active media market, providing a fertile ground for studying digital diplomacy efforts (Statista, 2025). With its high levels of digital participation, Brazil is a perfect case study for examining how influencer-led public diplomacy initiatives unfold in online spaces. As for France, its Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs (MEAE) has emphasized the central role of digital communication in the activities of its diplomatic network, aiming at pursuing 'digital soft diplomacy' (MEAE, 2022).

This study focuses on these specific cases that reflect observable trends in how public diplomacy operates in digital spaces, contributing both to understanding how influencers facilitate international engagement through digital platforms and to disentangling the interplay of cultural and diplomatic strategies within the Brazilian social media landscape. By examining these two countries, the study provides a comparative perspective on how different public diplomacy models adapt to Brazil's digital ecosystem.

The dataset used for this study consists of social media posts, videos, and audience comments from Instagram and TikTok. Given the limited presence of SMI-government collaborations in public diplomacy, this study adopted a comprehensive approach by analysing all social media posts published between April and November 2024 which met the following criteria: i) the post was shared on Instagram using the platform's official "Collaboration" feature, meaning the same post was simultaneously published on Paul Cabannes' account

(@paulcabannes_) and, at least one French diplomatic institution (e.g., embassy, consulate, cultural institution); ii) in addition to Instagram, the same post was also shared on Paul Cabannes (@paulcabannes_) TikTok account; iii) the post is publicly available on both platforms.

The decision to select posts that were primarily shared on Instagram using the official “Collaboration” feature is based on two main considerations: i) the feature implies a shared ownership of the content, with posts belonging to both Paul Cabannes’ and the French diplomatic institution’s profiles, representing a formal and equal partnership; and ii) French diplomatic institutions in Brazil do not have official TikTok accounts.

Despite this, analysing engagement and sentiment across both platforms is necessary. TikTok and Instagram cater to distinct audiences and employ different methods of content presentation, making it crucial to examine both for a comprehensive understanding of digital public diplomacy in Brazil. Analysing audience responses across these platforms provides insights into how diplomatic content circulates outside official channels and how influencers contribute to the organic reach and impact of public diplomacy initiatives.

During the seven-month period, Paul Cabannes published four collaborative posts with French diplomatic institutions on Instagram, which were also shared on TikTok. Therefore, the content analysis draws from four distinct influencer collaborations, each published on both Paul Cabannes’s Instagram (IG) and TikTok (TT) accounts (Table 4). However, for the purposes of the sentiment and comparative analysis, the dataset results in a total of eight posts, since each platform’s post has its own engagement rates and user comments, despite sharing the same content.

Table 4 - Overview of Paul Cabannes’ collaborations with French diplomatic institutions

Post #	Caption	Date of publishing	Engagement metrics	Diplomatic institution	Links
--------	---------	--------------------	--------------------	------------------------	-------

Post 1	“France vs Brazil”	04/29/2024	107.5K likes, 2.9K comments (IG) / 111.7K likes, 1K comments (TT)	French Embassy in Brazil	https://www.instagram.com/p/C6W6WpUp7C5/ (IG) https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes/video/7363331028628294918 (TT)
Post 2	“After all, it’s a beautiful partnership”	08/16/2024	32.7K likes, 1.4K comments / 34.6K likes, 520 comments (TT)	French Embassy in Brazil & Brazilian Embassy in France	https://www.instagram.com/p/C-u_SzcJ17h/ (IG) https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes/video/7403521184366742789 (TT)
Post 3	“That’s crazy”	11/07/2024	42.3K IG likes, 765 comments / 27.2K likes, 36,189 comments (TT)	French Embassy in Brazil & French Consulate in São Paulo	https://www.instagram.com/p/DCJ6TcepkhJ/ (IG) https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes/video/7434548949647641912 (TT)
Post 4	“Thank you to @Elysee”	11/20/2024	223.5K IG likes, 11.5K comments / 254.2K likes, 4.6K comments (TT)	French Embassy in Brazil & French Consulate in Rio de Janeiro	https://www.instagram.com/p/DCmMWLkpD2B/ (IG) https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes/video/7439372621596216631 (TT)

Note. Data collected from Paul Cabannes’ official Instagram (@paulcabannes_) and TikTok (@paulcabannes_) accounts.

The second phase of data collection focused on extracting audience comments for sentiment analysis after obtaining post details and engagement metrics. This study established a proportional 50% sample, based on simple random sampling as a probability sampling method, to analyse audience sentiment in a balanced and manageable manner. In total, 11,520 comments were collected, processed, and analysed: 8,280 from Instagram and 3,240 on TikTok.

The difference in sample size reflects the proportion of comments each post received on the respective platforms, with all samples representing 50% of the total comments (Table 5).

Table 5 - Comment sampling for sentiment analysis of Paul Cabannes' posts

Post #	IG comments (Total)	IG sampled (50%)	TT comments (Total)	TT sampled (50%)
Post 1	2,900	1,450	1,000	500
Post 2	1,400	700	520	260
Post 3	765	380	361	180
Post 4	11,500	5,750	4,600	2,300

Note. Data collected from Paul Cabannes' Instagram (@paulcabannes_) and TikTok (@paulcabannes_) accounts. Data represents interactions as of March 10, 2025.

The comment data was retrieved from TikTok and Instagram using Chrome extensions TTCommentExporter and IG Comment Export Tool before being transferred into Google Sheets. The datasets contained comment text, comment ID, username/nickname, and additional metadata. The data preparation started with a cleaning phase: the “Find duplicates” tool helped identify and eliminate duplicate entries, which consisted of identical comment text from the same user under the same comment ID. The “Randomize range” function in Google Sheets was used to randomize the comment text column, enabling random selection. The remaining unique comments were determined for each post by selecting an X number of comments (e.g. 700 out of 1,400), based on the established 50% sample.

3.2 Data analysis

The analysis is structured around three key methods. First, qualitative content analysis is used to explore themes, narratives, messaging, and engagement strategies in SMI-diplomatic collaborations. Second, sentiment analysis is employed to evaluate public perception and audience engagement with these initiatives. Third, comparative analysis assesses how

audiences on different social media platforms respond to the same influencer-driven public diplomacy strategies.

3.2.1 *Qualitative content analysis*

The content analysis was designed to determine how diplomatic themes were integrated in influencer-driven content and to analyse narrative techniques, messaging strategies, and institutional presence. Considering the small scale of posts to be analysed, no implementation of a coding method to conduct the content analysis was necessary. Instead, the analysis consisted of viewing, identifying and interpreting the content of the four posts published by Paul Cabannes in collaboration with French diplomatic institutions.

The analysis was structured around two main areas. First, *themes and messaging strategies* were identified, focusing on how French and Brazilian cultures were presented, the tone and style used in the messages (formal, informal, humorous, educational), and the main topics addressed in the discussion, including cultural exchange, bilateral relations, or diplomacy. Second, *institutional visibility* was measured through the level of government participation in the posted contents (direct participation, indirect participation), the way diplomatic institutions are represented in influencer collaborations, and whether government messages are seamlessly included in the content or overtly promotional.

Table 6 - Areas of content analysis

Area of analysis	Description
Cultural theme	Does the post highlight French culture, Brazilian culture, or both?
Messaging style	The tone is formal, humorous, or educational?
Main topic	What is the main focus of the post?
Government participation	Is the government directly or indirectly involved?

Government representation	How clearly are institutions shown? Prominent (clear presence), subtle (background), or hidden (not seen).
----------------------------------	--

Note. Table created by the author on March 22, 2025.

Overall, this analytical framework enabled a more specific examination of how influencer collaborations operate in the context of digital public diplomacy, particularly regarding message framing and institutional presence.

3.2.2 *Sentiment analysis*

To assess public perception, sentiment analysis of audience comments on selected posts was conducted. The sample was randomly extracted using Chrome extensions TTCommentExporter for TikTok (a tool for exporting TikTok comments) and IG Comment Export Tool for Instagram (which enables bulk comment extraction from Instagram posts).

The comments sentiment was classified manually to ensure accurate categorisation, and the data was structured in Google Sheets for direct comparison. Most comments were written in Portuguese, with a minor share written in French or English. To effectively analyse those written in French, Google Translator was used to ensure an accurate understanding. Comments were classified as positive, neutral or negative, explained in Table 7.

Table 7 - Sentiment analysis categorization

Sentiment category	Description
Positive	Express enthusiasm, admiration, or support for the content, the influencer, or the diplomatic collaboration.
Neutral	Express unclear emotional positions, personal opinions unrelated to the topic, tagging other users, factual observations, content suggestions, or comments with unclear meaning.
Negative	Express criticism, disagreement, scepticism, or hostility, targeting the content, the government, the influencer, or related political/cultural issues.

Note. Table created by the author on March 22, 2025.

This categorization examined how users respond differently to diplomatic content based on humour, cultural references and political themes, as well as established whether audience sentiment varies between platforms.

3.2.3 Comparative analysis

This study compares audience engagement and sentiment on TikTok and Instagram in the context of influencer-driven digitalized public diplomacy. Although the focus is on Paul Cabannes' collaborations with French diplomatic institutions, analysing both platforms helps to understand how different digital audiences receive and react to diplomatic messaging depending on the online settings.

Engagement metrics are used to compare the number of likes, comments and overall level of interaction on the two social media. This will also help determine which platform has a higher level of active participation in diplomatic conversations. Indeed, platform-specific trends will be compared to assess the public reception and engagement with the influencer-led diplomacy. This way, the research helps determine whether one platform fosters more interactive discussions as compared to the other. This is particularly relevant to the case study, given France's diplomatic institutions absence on TikTok, hence showing if there is potential for reaching and engaging new audiences in this platform.

While this comparative approach provides a nuanced perspective on how influencer diplomacy works across different digital spaces, highlighting platform-specific behaviours and their implications for diplomatic communication strategies, the study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the limited number of the case study's collaborations restricts the generalisability of the findings. Second, some engagement data (e.g., hidden comments, restricted views) are not accessible due to platform policies. This may affect the comparability of findings and replicability. As for the sentiment analysis, this is language-

dependent and cultural nuances (e.g., sarcasm and slangs) could have gone missed from the overall interpretation of the message.

Despite these limitations, this study offers a systematic and comparative analysis of influencer diplomacy, contributing to the understanding of how the foreign public diplomacy adapts to digital platforms.

Chapter 4: Case study - Paul Cabannes and France's digital public diplomacy in Brazil

In this chapter, the professional life of Aime Paul Henri Cabannes, or simply, Paul Cabannes, a French comedian and a social media influencer (SMI) will be discussed. His career in Brazil is a good example to analyse for this research. His biography, social media contents, and collaborations with French diplomatic institutions will be examined to ascertain how his digital presence enriches France's public diplomacy in Brazil.

4.1 Introduction to Paul Cabannes

Since 2015, French comedian, content creator, and social media influencer Paul Cabannes has established himself as a successful comedian in Brazil. After moving to São Paulo, he first worked as a French tutor before launching his YouTube channel in 2017. In his early content, he made humorous videos that compared the cultural differences between Brazil and France. He realized the potential to transition into stand-up comedy when his videos started getting more than 70,000 views, and he began performing in small bar venues before moving on to larger stages (Calmon, 2023).

Figure 2 - Paul Cabannes creating content

Note. Paul Cabannes, que tem milhões de seguidores no TikTok e Instagram. Photograph by Zanone Fraissat/Folhapress. Retrieved from <https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/folhateen/2023/05/paul-cabannes-odeia-audios-e-croissant-recheado-mas-adora-o-brasil-e-o-sucesso-que-faz-aqui.shtml>.

He has also put a lot of effort into creating his presence on other platforms apart from YouTube. Currently, his social media analytics show his popularity, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8 - Paul Cabannes's social media followers

Platform	Handle	Followers
Instagram	@paulcabannes_	2.3M followers
Threads	@paulcabannes_	525K followers
TikTok	@paulcabannes_	2.4M followers
YouTube	@PaulCabannes	1.51M subscribers
X	@paulcabannes_	2.089 followers

Note. Data retrieved from Paul Cabannes' social media accounts. Numbers are accurate as of March 12, 2025.

Through video-based content, Paul Cabannes has established a large following across Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. Through his comedic approach, he uses cultural humor to mock stereotypes, linguistic quirks, and everyday misunderstandings between French and Brazilian cultures. His content explores Brazilian slang, croissant etiquette, and Brazilian traditions, which aim to engage viewers while making the content relatable (Franco 2023).

Cabannes has demonstrated success in live events by touring major Brazilian cities and performing internationally in Lisbon and Paris (A Tarde, 2023; ABC Reporter, 2025). His comedic observations serve as an informal cultural diplomacy tool that promotes France-Brazil dialogue while breaking down cultural stereotypes (Ouest-France, 2024; 20 Minutes, 2024). His work is consistent with the current concepts of digital public diplomacy, demonstrating how social media influencers can function as non-state actors to enhance people-to-people interactions (Zaharna 2009).

4.1.1 Cabannes' role in public diplomacy and engagement with French institutions

Cabannes is increasingly more recognized within diplomatic circles, highlighting his contributions as a non-state actor in France's public diplomacy in Brazil. In 2024, he collaborated in digitalized public diplomacy strategies with the French Embassy in Brazil and consulates. His visibility in diplomatic spaces is evident through social media interactions with French representatives, as illustrated in the following example. In September 2024, Caroline Putnoki, the South America Director of ATOUT France (France Tourism Development Agency), shared an Instagram post featuring Paul Cabannes and Érick Jacquin, a renowned French chef widely known in Brazil as a MasterChef Brazil judge, at the General Consulate of France in São Paulo (Figure 3). The post received 19.9K likes and 213 comments, with Putnoki captioning: *"I met at the General Consulate last week with the two most well-known and irresistible Frenchmen in Brazil. Pleasure to meet you in person, @paulcabannes_, and always great to see you again, @erickjacquin #FranceInBrazil #BrazilTheFrenchWay.*

Figure 3 - Paul Cabannes with Caroline Putnoki and Érick Jacquin at the General Consulate of France in São Paulo.

Note. Image from Putnoki, C. [@carolineputnokiocial]. (2024, September 24). *Encontrei no Consulado Geral, na semana passada, com os dois Franceses FR mais conhecidos...* [Instagram post]. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DAUMmkKSABC/>.

Later, in November 2024, Putnoki shared another Instagram post featuring Cabannes at the 2024 French Cinema Varilux Festival in São Paulo, which received over 12K likes and 376 comments (Figure 4). The caption emphasized his cultural significance, stating:

At the Varilux Festival, @variluxcinefrances, some lively conversations moderated by @alexandramias, the Consul General of France @sp.fr, between the most popular Frenchman in Brazil and the most popular Brazilian in France! Congratulations @rai10oficial and @paulcabannes_. Merci @jeanphilippeperol for capturing this euphoric moment #BrazilTheFrenchWay.

Figure 4 - Paul Cabannes at the 2024 French Cinema Varilux Festival

Note. Image from Putnoki, C. [@carolineputnokioficial]. (2024, November 6). *No Festival Varilux, @variluxcinefrances uns papos animados moderados pela...* [Instagram post]. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DAUMmkKSABC/>.

An analysis of Putnoki's Instagram engagement data between September 2024 and February 2025 (Figure 5) reveals that her interactions with Cabannes generated an increase in her profile's engagement rate. This suggests that his involvement in diplomatic and cultural events significantly enhanced the digital reach of French institutions.

Figure 5 - Average Engagements of @carolineputnokioficial on Instagram (September 2024 – February 2025)

Note. Data retrieved from @carolineputnokioficial on Instagram. Analysis conducted by Influencer Analytics by Wednesday⁴ on March 11, 2025.

A similar effect was observed during Cabannes' collaborations with the French Embassy and consulates in Brazil, which significantly boosted the engagement rates of their institutional profiles. These collaborations marked a high point in his involvement with diplomatic initiatives, culminating in an invitation to an official event with French President Emmanuel Macron.

Cabannes' meeting with President Macron and public diplomacy visibility

In November 2024, Cabannes was invited to attend an official meeting with French President Emmanuel Macron during the G20 Summit in Brazil. Their conversation was shared online and received media coverage. The moment was documented in a post by *Folha de S.Paulo*, which shared a photo of the two together (Figure 6).

⁴Influencer Analytics by Wednesday is a free Chrome extension designed to provide in-depth analytics and creator discovery tools for influencer marketing. It offers detailed profile insights, allowing users to analyze engagement metrics, audience demographics, and content performance directly within their browser.

Figure 6 - French comedian Paul Cabannes and French President Emmanuel Macron discussing croissants in a humorous exchange

Note. [Photograph]. *Folha de S.Paulo*, 2024. Retrieved from <https://f5.folha.uol.com.br/voceviu/2024/11/croissant-pode-ter-recheio-presidente-frances-responde-que-nao.shtml>.

As for the light relief, Cabannes once again illustrated his humor during their conversation, amusing everyone with his question about croissants: *“I’ve been defending the idea for nine years that croissants should be eaten without any filling. [...] What is France’s official stance on this?”* To which Macron responded: *“It is clear, it allows no exceptions—it’s plain. Because in a butter croissant, there is no filling”* (as cited in Delage, 2024, translated by the author).

This humorous yet diplomatically relevant conversation inspired online discussions in the comments, further reinforcing Cabannes’ status as an informal but effective public diplomacy actor. His presence at the G20 Summit has solidified his influence as a familiar figure in France’s soft power strategy in Brazil (Le Parisien, 2024).

4.2 France's public diplomacy strategy in Brazil

Brazil and France share an enduring diplomatic friendship, officially elevated to a strategic partnership in May 2006 by Presidents Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva and Jacques Chirac (Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires étrangères, 2024). This partnership recognized Brazil as a global actor and a valid candidate for a permanent seat on the UN Security Council, which facilitated the exchange of expertise and resources in various areas, including military cooperation, space research, energy development, economic relations, education, environmental policies, and cross-border collaboration (Araújo & Milani, 2011).

The French mission in Brazil has a network that includes an Embassy in Brasília, consulates in São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, and Recife, and 18 honorary consulates (Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires étrangères, 2024). Cultural diplomacy has been a cornerstone of France's public diplomacy strategy abroad, with a particular focus on education, the arts, and language promotion (Melissen, 2005). This was followed by another significant initiative in Brazil, the *Ano da França no Brasil* (Year of France in Brazil) in 2009, which had more than 560 projects, including exhibitions, concerts, film screenings, and academic exchanges in over 200 cities across the country (Oliveira, 2010). This large-scale initiative enhanced diplomatic, cultural, and economic relations between France and Brazil to strengthen France's cultural influence in Brazil.

The dissemination of the French language is also an important part of the cooperation between the two countries. There are three French lycées in São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro and Brasília and more than 2,500 students including 1,500 French nationals (Agence pour l'Enseignement Français à l'Étranger, 2024). The Alliance Française in Brazil, the biggest in the world, has 37 associations and 63 units and receives 24,000 students every year (Alliance Française, 2024).

Established in 2009, the digital library La France au Brésil helps promote cultural diplomacy by providing free access to historical documents, maps, manuscripts and photographs of the France-Brazil relations of the last four centuries (UNESCO, 2024). The editorial sector is also very important, and Brazil is the biggest market for French books in South America, testifying strong connections between Brazilian and French publishers (Ministère de la Culture, 2024). France and Brazil will reach 200 years of diplomatic relations in 2025 through the France-Brazil Season, a one-year program of cultural and creative collaborations (Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires étrangères, 2024). It will be an important public diplomacy event to look back at the past and instigate future cooperation in the fields of art, education, and science.

4.2.1 Digital diplomacy initiatives

Digital diplomacy is becoming more crucial for France, and the country has gradually incorporated it into its public diplomacy strategies (Pamment, 2016). The French diplomatic network in Brazil uses social media platforms such as Instagram, X (former Twitter), and YouTube to engage the Brazilian public, disseminate cultural content, and share diplomatic updates. However, an analysis of their social media accounts shows different levels of activity and engagement depending on the institution (Table 9).

Table 9 - Social media presence of French diplomatic institutions in Brazil

France's Diplomatic institution	Number of followers / subscribers		
	X	Instagram	YouTube
Embassy in Brasília	15,4K followers	57,6K followers	827 subscribers
Consulate-General in São Paulo	1,1K followers	16,9K followers	612 subscribers
Consulate-General in Rio de Janeiro	379 followers	14,7K followers	5 subscribers
Consulate-General in Recife	143 followers	7,2K followers	48 subscribers
Honorary Consulate in Aracaju	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Belém	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Belo Horizonte	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Campinas	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Curitiba	No	167 followers	No
Honorary Consulate in Florianópolis	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Fortaleza	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Foz do Iguaçu	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Macapá	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Maceió	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Manaus	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Natal	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Porto Alegre	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Salvador	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Santos	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in São José dos Campos	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in São Luís	No	No	No
Honorary Consulate in Vitória	No	No	No

Note. Data collected from official social media accounts of French diplomatic institutions in Brazil.

Follower and subscriber counts are accurate as of March 10, 2025.

Sources: Embassy of France in Brasília, Consulates-General of France in São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, and Recife, and honorary consulates.

The digital diplomacy of France in Brazil operates from the Brasília Embassy, which acts as a centralized hub for managing social media platforms. The digital engagement of regional consulates remains minimal while honorary consulates maintain no online presence. The French diplomatic efforts in Brazil through digital platforms show their highest development on Instagram. The Embassy in Brasília maintains the largest following with 57.6K followers, surpassing all other consulates. The São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro consulates maintain mid-range follower counts (16.9K and 14.7K), whereas Recife and Curitiba have smaller follower bases. The absence of active honorary consulates except Curitiba, which has only 167 followers, demonstrates that Instagram functions as a centralized communication platform that mostly targets capital and major cities, with minor efforts to connect with regional audiences.

The number of followers on France's X (Twitter) account in Brazil is substantially lower than its follower count on Instagram. The Embassy in Brasília maintains the highest following, but its 15,400 followers account for only a quarter of its total Instagram audience. Every consulate has fewer than 2,000 Twitter followers, while none of the honorary consulates use the platform.

YouTube serves as the platform with the lowest level of utilization. The Brasília Embassy leads YouTube subscription numbers, however, with only 827 subscribers. The Rio de Janeiro Consulate's account has only five subscribers, while all other consulates remain inactive on the platform. Therefore, this platform's capabilities for storytelling and education through longer-form content remain unexploited by France, possibly indicating that creating video content is a lower priority in their digital strategy.

Overall, French public diplomacy in Brazil operates mainly through Instagram, where the Embassy in Brasília maintains a central role. The platforms X (Twitter) and YouTube receive insufficient attention, which results in small levels of user interaction. The French

network of honorary consulates (which spans more than 20 cities) remains offline, creating a substantial deficiency in France's digital outreach to regional areas.

On another note, their interaction rate is quite different, especially on Instagram, where French institutions appear to attract the most audience engagement. The social media presence of French diplomatic missions in Brazil varies in terms of activity and outreach (Table 10).

Table 10 - Engagement metrics of French diplomatic institutions on Instagram

French institution	Followers	Average likes	Average comments
Embassy of France in Brasília @franceaubresil	57,6K followers	3K	273
Consulate-General of France in São Paulo @sp.fr	16,9K followers	316	9,88
Consulate-General of France in Rio de Janeiro @francanorio	14,7K followers	4.2K	51.25
Consulate-General of France in Recife @nordeste.fr	7,2K followers	808	30,9

Note. Data extracted using Influencer Analysis by Wednesday extension. Follower counts, average likes, and average comments reflect engagement levels as of March 10, 2025.

Sources: Official Instagram accounts of French diplomatic institutions in Brasília, São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, and Recife.

The Embassy in Brasília has the highest number of followers among French diplomatic missions in Brazil; however, its engagement rates are lower compared to those of the Consulate General of France in Rio de Janeiro. Despite having less than half the followers of the Embassy, the Rio de Janeiro Consulate achieves significantly higher interactions per post. Furthermore, passive engagement (i.e., likes) surpasses active engagement (i.e., comments), indicating that promoting online conversations has been proven difficult to achieve.

While the French Embassy in Brasília maintains a significant online presence, its outreach is comparatively lower than that of other diplomatic missions in Brazil, including Japan (@embaixadajapao with 112K followers on IG), Germany (@alemanhanobrasil with

108K followers on IG) and the United States of America (@embaixadaUSA with 188K followers on IG). The French Consulate in São Paulo, one of Brazil's major financial and cultural centers, has only 1.1K followers on Instagram. This highlights the need for more effective digital engagement strategies to enhance its reach and impact. The limited visibility of the Consulate in Recife and the absence of digital activity from honorary consulates open possibilities for improvement in France's digital public diplomacy.

4.3 Content analysis: Themes and messaging

Paul Cabannes' content demonstrates that SMIs can serve as non-state actors and opinion leaders in public diplomacy, particularly when it comes to cultural engagement between France and Brazil. His collaboration with French diplomatic institutions fits within a relational approach to public diplomacy (Zaharna, 2009), which emphasizes dialogue, cultural exchange, and audience engagement over one-way communication.

All four collaborations maintain a distinct identity, with Cabannes engaging humorous cultural observations, his signature catchphrases (including his frequent use of the phrase "*I'm leaving*"), and his personal struggles with Portuguese, particularly when deciphering colloquial Brazilian Portuguese expressions. Unlike conventional diplomatic communication, which uses formal and institutional messages, Cabannes' content incorporates potential diplomatic themes (e.g., cultural differences and curiosities) into everyday cultural discourse, with light and comedic undertones.

This section examines the four posts analysed in detail, focusing on their thematic structure, messaging strategies, and how they integrate into France's broader digital public diplomacy.

Table 11 - Results of content analysis

Post #	Cultural theme	Messaging style	Main topic	Government participation	Government representation
--------	----------------	-----------------	------------	--------------------------	---------------------------

Post 1	It highlights French and Brazilian culture	Formal and humorous	Bilateral relations and personal preferences	Directly involved	Subtle (in the background)
Post 2	It highlights French and Brazilian culture	Informal and humorous	Bilateral relations and sports rivalry	Directly involved	Subtle (in the background)
Post 3	It highlights French and Brazilian culture	Informal, humorous and educational	Cultural exchange, culinary, and language	Indirectly involved	Hidden (not seen)
Post 4	It highlights mostly French culture	Formal and humorous	Diplomacy and soft power	Directly involved	Prominent (clear presence)

Note. Table created by the author on March 22, 2025.

The first post, under the caption “France vs Brazil” was published on April 29, 2024, in Paul Cabannes and the French Embassy in Brazil IG’s accounts, and at the same time in Paul Cabannes TikTok account. This post uses satire in a formal setting in its approach to cultural diplomacy, offering a humorous comparison between France and Brazil, highlighting both cultures.

Figure 7 - Collaborative Post #1 on Instagram

Note. Screenshot from Instagram (@paulcabannes_), April 29, 2024.

The video is filmed in front of French and Brazilian flags, and the setting is a question-and-answer session where Cabannes is asked by an embassy's representative in the background to choose between French and Brazilian culture (such as *croissant* vs. *pão de queijo*, *rugby* vs. *football*, *cassoulet* vs. *feijoada*). At first, he picks the Brazilian ones, but when told that this is the French Embassy, he starts to deliberately pick French and emphasize the difference between the two.

Humour is used in this post to involve audiences in supporting the idea of cultural identity without having to promote one nation over the other, thus creating a humorous discourse about cultural preferences. The sarcastic moment when he gives in and chooses Dunkirk Carnival over Rio Carnival demonstrates how irony is used in diplomatic humour to

engage the audience and make them think about how national and cultural biases influence our perceptions.

In terms of public diplomacy, this post makes France's cultural presence in Brazil a conversation rather than a marketing campaign so that the audience can join in the discussion of cultural identity. Instead of giving a one-dimensional view of France, the content aims to incite conversation through comedy and thus maintains France's presence in Brazil's digital realm in a comprehensible manner.

The second post, under the caption "After all, it's a beautiful partnership", was published on August 16, 2024, on Paul Cabannes, the French Embassy in Brazil and the Brazilian Embassy in France's Instagram accounts, as well as on Paul Cabannes's TikTok account. This post was a collaboration involving both the French Embassy in Brazil and the Brazilian Embassy in France, with Cabannes acting as network bridge between the two diplomatic institutions. Similarly to the first post, it displays a formal satire in its approach to cultural diplomacy, offering a humorous comparison between France and Brazil, highlighting both cultures. Governmental representatives of both embassies are directly involved, participating in the background.

Figure 8 - Collaborative Post #2 on Instagram

Note. Screenshot from Instagram (@paulcabannes_), August 16, 2024.

Adopting a mock diplomatic debate format where the two sides playfully argue over cultural superiority, by discussing preferences, including landmarks (Champs-Élysées vs. Copacabana), food traditions (croissant vs. coxinha), and punctuality (French vs. Brazilian timekeeping). As suggested by the use of humour, a formal diplomatic dialogue is made informal and livelier, following Grunig and Hunt's (1984) two-way symmetrical communication model, which is dialogue-based rather than a monologue. The debate continues up to a diplomatic draw, a balanced narrative, until a football-related question (Neymar vs. Mbappé) makes Cabannes laugh and refuse to answer, showing how sports can engage people passionately in diplomacy.

From a public diplomacy perspective, this post reinforces the idea of France-Brazil relations as an equal partnership, positioning diplomacy as a shared cultural exchange rather

than a top-down institutional effort. The inclusion of both embassies fosters credibility, making this collaboration an example of how influencer-led diplomacy can effectively engage diverse audiences.

The third post, under the caption “That’s crazy,” was published on November 9, 2024, on both Paul Cabannes, the French Embassy in Brazil and French Consulate in São Paulo’s Instagram accounts, as well as on Paul Cabannes’s TikTok account. This post was a collaboration involving both the French Embassy in Brazil and the French Consulate in São Paulo, although no direct governmental representation or participation is shown. It highlights both cultures in an informal matter, as it takes a linguistic and cultural approach with the help of humor, revealing the mutual impact of French and Brazilian societies.

Figure 9 - Collaborative Post #3 on Instagram

Note. Screenshot from Instagram (@paulcabannes_), November 9, 2024.

Set in a traditional Brazilian bar, the video features Cabannes and his friend Osvaldo⁵, who stage a humorous debate about loanwords used in Brazilian Portuguese that are of French origin. The structure of the video follows a repeating comedic pattern: Osvaldo introduces a word that is widely used in Brazil, such as *menu*, *purée*, or *petit gâteau*, and Cabannes responds by confirming that the word is actually French. The joke becomes more intense when Osvaldo sarcastically ends by claiming that it is the French who have copied from Brazil, a reversal of the usual Eurocentric narrative of cultural dominance.

This post is particularly successful in soft power diplomacy (Nye 2004) because it plays with the fluidity of cultural exchange instead of reinforcing strict national categorizations. The humor engages the audience, and people are likely to comment about other words that are present in both languages, thus extending the discussion beyond the video itself. From a public diplomacy viewpoint, this content does not feel like a language promotion advertisement, which can sometimes appear too artificial and resemble propaganda. Instead, it demonstrates the linguistic relations between France and Brazil in a way that looks organic, fun, and natural to the audience.

The fourth post, under the caption “Thank you to @Elysee,” was published on November 20, 2024, on both Paul Cabannes, the French Embassy in Brazil and the French Consulate in Rio de Janeiro’s Instagram accounts, as well as on Paul Cabannes’s TikTok account. This post was a collaboration involving the French Embassy in Brazil and the French Consulate in Rio de Janeiro, as the video was recorded during the 2024 G20 Summit in the city. It uses a form of formal satire in its approach to cultural diplomacy, blending humour, diplomacy, and soft power to highlight the relationship between France and Brazil, but mostly reflecting French culture.

⁵ Osvaldo Barros is a Brazilian comedian and digital content creator who frequently collaborates with Paul Cabannes in satirical videos about cultural and linguistic differences between Brazil and France.

Figure 10 - Collaborative Post #4 on Instagram

Note. Screenshot from Instagram (@paulcabannes_), November 20, 2024.

This post is the most politically significant in the dataset, with Cabannes talking face-to-face with French President Emmanuel Macron during the G20 Summit in Brazil. Therefore, France's representation is direct and prominent. Formal diplomacy is not often involved with influencer-driven content, but this post shows how political figures can be incorporated into digital-first communication plans.

The video starts with the discussion of hospitality in Brazil, with Macron saying that all his impressions of the country are positive, as it is a welcoming place. The dialogue continues with a comic diplomatic conversation about croissants, where Cabannes wants to know from Macron whether the French government can make a statement that croissants should only be eaten plain. Macron repeats the traditional French view on croissants and then, good-naturedly,

concedes that sticking your croissant in your coffee is okay, something that Cabannes looks downright horrified by.

This combination of lightness with seriousness of formal diplomacy reflects the evolution of the practice in the contemporary world, consistent with social listening approaches (Cull, 2019), which allow political figures to address digital audiences in unconventional ways. Humour can be a key component of France's strategy for making diplomacy relatable, thus making France's diplomatic presence more appealing and exercising soft power through the humanization of state actors.

4.4 Engagement metrics and sentiment analysis

The evaluation of engagement is essential when measuring digital public diplomacy efforts, particularly when SMIs are involved, in order to examine audience which strategies are better received by foreign audiences. The following section introduces an overview of engagement patterns on both Instagram and TikTok, followed by an analysis of audience sentiment through sampled comments from each platform.

4.5.1 Engagement metrics across posts

One of the main purposes of this study is to determine if it is possible to increase engagement through partnerships between SMIs and official diplomatic institutions. By comparing the posts of Paul Cabannes to the engagement rates of different French diplomatic agencies in Brazil, this analysis assesses the effectiveness of using influencers to enhance digital public diplomacy and engagement. As outlined in Section 4.2.1, French diplomatic institutions in Brazil have limited engagement on social media, where few posts receive more than 4K likes and fewer comments than 300. This creates a challenge for promoting audience interaction, unless they are politically active or already interested in French culture.

The data, as illustrated in Table 8, shows that Cabannes' collaborative posts exceeded the average engagement of French diplomatic institutions and supports the idea that influencer

collaborations on social media can enhance diplomatic visibility and interaction with the foreign audiences. Even the least-engaged influencer post (Post 3) received over 69K likes, which accounts for more than 20 times the average engagement on the French Embassy’s Instagram account. Post 4, featuring President Emmanuel Macron, raised the engagement by 16,000% compared to the Embassy’s normal rates, receiving 477.7K likes and 16.1K comments.

Table 8 - Influencer-driven engagement compared to institutional averages

Post #	Likes	Comments	Collaborating institution(s)	Increase compared to institution’s average likes (3k)
Post 1 – “France vs. Brazil”	219.2K	3.9K	French Embassy in Brazil	+7,206%
Post 2 – “After all, it’s a beautiful partnership”	67.3K	1.9K	French Embassy in Brazil & Brazilian Embassy in France	+2,143%
Post 3 – “That’s crazy”	69.5K	1.1K	French Embassy in Brazil & French Consulate in São Paulo	+2,217%
Post 4 – “Thank you to @Elysee”	477.7K	16.1K	French Embassy in Brazil & French Consulate in Rio de Janeiro	+15,923%

Note. Engagement metrics (likes and comments) collected from Paul Cabannes’ official Instagram (@paulcabannes_) and TikTok (@paulcabannes_) accounts. The percentage increase in engagement was calculated by comparing post performance to the average number of likes (3K) on posts from the French Embassy in Brazil (@franceaubresil). Data was retrieved on March 10, 2025, using Influencer Analysis by Wednesday extension.

By comparing these institutional rates with the engagement levels of Cabannes’ collaborative posts, a significant increase in audience interaction is evident in posts published in collaboration with Paul Cabannes. Therefore, this analysis shows that public diplomacy strategies in partnership by SMIs can greatly improve digital engagement, as opposed to the conventional diplomatic communication.

4.5.2 Sentiment analysis

As explained in Chapter 3, all comments on the four posts, both on Instagram and TikTok, were categorized into three sentiment groups: positive, neutral, and negative. In total 11,500 comments were manually analysed and categorized according to sentiments they expressed.

4.5.2.1 Sentiment analysis - Post #1 – “France vs Brazil”

Figure 11 displays the sentiment of comments received by the “France vs Brazil” post on Instagram and TikTok.

Figure 11 - Sentiment analysis of Post #1 on Instagram and TikTok

Note. Chart created by the author on March 22, 2025.

This post had strong positive engagement across both platforms, particularly on Instagram, where 71% of the comments were positive. The humorous tone of the post, which featured Cabannes comparing French and Brazilian cultural elements in a satirical manner, could have contributed to its widespread audience appreciation. Some commentators even shared personal stories related to France:

*My daughter has been passionate about France since she was little! For her 15th birthday, she asked for a trip to Paris! We went, and she came back enchanted. She took online classes on her own and later studied for her undergraduate degree in Lyon! She also did her master's there! She has been living there for 8 years now! Now, we visit her in Paris every two years! I am very grateful to France!*⁶

The similar neutral comments percentage on Instagram (38.14%) and TikTok (26%) mostly include brief statements or observations without strong opinions. Some individuals shared curiosities about topics mentioned in the video, complementing the information and bringing more knowledge into comments discussions. One example regards the Dunkirk Carnival, when the Embassy representative asks Cabannes “*What do you prefer? Rio Carnaval or Dunkirk Carnaval?*” to which he responds “*Dunkirk*”, in a sarcastic tone and joking about the common rainy weather when the event happens. The netizen adds:

I have been living in Dunkirk for 14 years. Dunkirk is located in the Hauts-de-France department, in the Nord region (not in Normandy). It is historically known for being the site of Operation Dynamo during World War II, as depicted in Nolan's film. The Dunkirk Carnival is a centuries-old tradition that began as a celebration held before men departed for fishing trips to Iceland. Since they would spend months at sea, uncertain of their return, they threw a huge party with men dressing as women, plenty of smoked fish, and alcohol! The tradition has endured, and today, carnival festivities in the region last nearly three months, from late January to March, featuring street bands and organized balls with their own unique customs. The peak of the carnival coincides with

⁶ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' Instagram post, “France vs. Brazil”, published on April 29, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6W6WpUp7C5/> on March 10, 2025.

*Brazil's Carnival dates, attracting visitors from all over France and beyond. It's a lot of fun!*⁷

The negative comment percentage remained low (7.72% on IG and 3% on TT), but Instagram showed more than the double of negative comments than on TikTok. Criticisms primarily focusing on the choice of Brazilian cultural representations mentioned in the video. For instance, the choice of adding the famous Brazilian singer Anitta to the “What do you prefer?” question, between her and Aya Nakamura, raised several criticisms from individuals who felt unrepresented by her. However, some criticisms also cover political questions:

*The French Embassy in Brazil, with support from the diplomatic representations of Italy and Germany, worked in Congress to remove the mandatory Spanish requirement from the New High School Curriculum. This information was confirmed by the embassies to CNN. I saw this report on CNN and just wanted to understand your interest in ensuring that Brazilian schools are not required to offer Spanish?*⁸

This comment refers to a decision by the Brazilian Chamber of Deputies in July 2024 to remove Spanish as a mandatory subject, as part of a project of law that changes the rules for the country's high school education system (Behnke, 2024). The decision was supported by a lobby of French, German and Italian diplomatic representatives in Brazil. These embassies argued that without the mandatory Spanish requirement, schools would have the option to offer

⁷ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' Instagram post, "France vs. Brazil," published on April 29, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6W6WpUp7C5/> on March 10, 2025.

⁸ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' Instagram post, “France vs. Brazil”, published on April 29, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6W6WpUp7C5/> on March 10, 2025.

a second language if they choose to or if there is a state or municipal mandate (Deutsche Welle, 2024). This comment was left unanswered by both Cabannes and the French Embassy in Brazil.

4.5.2.2 Sentiment analysis - Post #2 – "After all, it's a beautiful partnership".

Figure 12 shows the audience's sentiment associated with comments posted on "After all, it's a beautiful partnership" post on Instagram and TikTok.

Figure 12 - Sentiment analysis of Post #2 on Instagram and TikTok

Note. Chart created by the author on March 22, 2025.

This post followed a similar sketch as the previous one, reinforcing humour-based content comparing France and Brazil, this time accompanied by both French and Brazilian diplomatic representatives. The post was well-received by audiences on both platforms, particularly on Instagram where 59.14% of comments were categorized as positive, in contrast with 48.85% on TikTok. Some individuals praised Cabannes and were happily surprised by the partnership with both embassies as exemplified: "*Hahaha, unbelievable — he actually*

manages to post this with the support of two embassies!"⁹. On TikTok, a user praised the format of the content: *"It was brilliant the way he positioned himself between the two flags — maybe showing that he has a bit of both cultures haha"*¹⁰.

The bilateral diplomatic structure of this post, featuring both the French and Brazilian embassies, encouraged discussions around cultural diplomacy and national identity, mostly focused on sports icon biases in Favor of one country over the other (Neymar vs. Mbappé). These comments followed up on the question *"Who do you prefer? Neymar or Mbappé?"*, to which Cabannes left unanswered as the video ends. Both soccer players' admirers dominated the Neutral category of comments, particularly on Instagram (43.85%).

Negative comments were the minority, with TikTok receiving 7.31% of them, more than double from Instagram (3.43%). On a similar note, as the previous post, they mostly consisted of criticism over Brazilian cultural representations on the video, particularly targeting the inclusion of Brazilian drag queen singer Pablllo Vittar at Madonna's 2024 concert in Copacabana, Rio de Janeiro, as exemplified: *"You ruined it when you mentioned Pablllo Vittar and Madonna."*¹¹ These responses were categorized as hate comments due to their discriminatory and hostile tone.

4.5.2.3 Sentiment analysis - Post #3 – "That's crazy".

⁹ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' Instagram post, "After all, it's a beautiful partnership" published on August 16, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.instagram.com/p/C-u_SzcJl7h/ on March 10, 2025.

¹⁰ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' TikTok post, "After all, it's a beautiful partnership" published on August 16, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7403521184366742789 on March 10, 2025.

¹¹ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' TikTok post, "After all, it's a beautiful partnership" published on August 16, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7403521184366742789 on March 10, 2025.

Figure 13 displays the sentiment of comments to the “That’s crazy” post on Instagram and TikTok.

Figure 13 - Sentiment analysis of Post #3 on Instagram and TikTok

Note. Chart created by the author on March 22, 2025.

This post, which humorously explored linguistic similarities between French and Brazilian Portuguese, received a high proportion of positive comments on TikTok (64.44%) and Instagram (52.37%). Audience reactions centred on appreciation for cultural exchange and recognition of shared linguistic heritage. One netizen highlighted: “*I didn’t know that ‘puree’ and ‘menu’ came from French!*”¹² showcasing a potential for informing through humour, as a complement to engaging audiences.

Neutral comments (41.84% on IG, 32.78% on TT) were often statements of factual observations rather than active discussions: “*That’s why I already enrolled my son in French*

¹² Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, “That’s crazy” published on August 16, 2024.

Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7434548949647641912 on March 10, 2025.

classes”¹³. The percentage of negative comments (5.79% on IG, 2.78% on TT) was lower on TikTok if compared to previous posts, but around the same level on Instagram. Some users spread negative stereotypes about French people, like “*Nobody showers there*”¹⁴ and “*Arrogant just like a Frenchmen at the end*”¹⁵. These types of comments, although can be deemed as uninteresting for political and diplomatic affairs, reveal cultural biases potentially hurtful for mutual understanding and soft power purposes.

4.5.2.4 Sentiment analysis - Post #4 – “Thank you to @elysee”.

Lastly, Figure 14 shows the sentiment of comments to the “Thank you to @elysee” post on Instagram and TikTok.

¹³ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ Instagram post, “That’s crazy” published on August 16, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7434548949647641912 on March 10, 2025.

¹⁴ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ Instagram post, “That’s crazy” published on August 16, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DCJ6TcepkhJ/> on March 10, 2025.

¹⁵ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ Instagram post, “That’s crazy” published on August 16, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DCJ6TcepkhJ/> on March 10, 2025.

Figure 14 - Sentiment analysis of Post #4 on Instagram and TikTok

Note. Chart created by the author on March 22, 2025.

The post featuring President Emmanuel Macron and spoken in French (with Brazilian Portuguese subtitles) breached Cabanne’s traditionally Brazilian audience, reaching several French netizens, particularly on TikTok. Macron’s collaboration on the video, enabled by the G20 Summit in Brazil, contributed to an outstanding positive reception (83.52% on IG; 69.78% on TT), particularly among Instagram users. The French President’s official TikTok and Instagram accounts added a comment on the post: *“I’m sure we’ll find an agreement on the croissant”*¹⁶.

Comments by Brazilian netizens represented the highest number of positive reactions, with most users showcasing being impressed and happy for Cabannes’ opportunity to meet the French President:

¹⁶ French President Emmanuel Macron commented on Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, in response to the humorous diplomatic exchange about croissant etiquette. The comment was posted on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631.

*I don't know what's more incredible—Paul becoming so famous in Brazil that he got an audience with the President of France, or the President himself joining in on Paul's joke. Genius! He even pretended to leave, and the amazing, charming President played along! Paul is teaching France to embrace the fun without limits. Love it!*¹⁷

The neutral comment percentage was balanced across platforms (12.66% on IG; 15.75% on TT). Some netizens curiously inquired about French viewers and if the humour in the video reflects the French culture: *“And did the French watch it too? I'm curious to know if a good-humored President represents them — or is that kind of humor lost on them? Was the idea for the meeting yours or his?”*¹⁸

Negative comments on TikTok were also the highest across all posts for TikTok, accounting for 14.57% in contrast for only 3.83% on Instagram. Among negative comments written by Brazilian users, many discussions were raised over a decision of Alexandre Bompard, the CEO of the French retail group Carrefour, to stop selling meat produced by countries in the Mercosur trade bloc, including Brazil, in France. Bompard stated that the company was protesting against a trade agreement being negotiated between the Mercosur bloc and the European Union, claiming that the agreement would flood France with low-quality meat that does not meet the country's standards.

Macron and Cabannes, although not directly involved in the issue, received several critics, as exemplified: *“Now ask him why Brazilian meat isn't good enough for the French*

¹⁷ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' Instagram post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DCmMWLkpD2B/> on March 10, 2025.

¹⁸ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes' Instagram post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DCmMWLkpD2B/> on March 10, 2025.

people”¹⁹ and “He lives in our culture and didn’t ask the most important question: the boycott of Brazilian meat by French farmers and the fact that Grupo Carrefour Brazil stopped buying national meat”²⁰. Other negative comments from Brazilian users reveal discontent with France’s history of colonialism in Africa: “Yikes, stopped following. One of the most deceitful guys in the world. He enslaves Africa—African peoples still suffer today from the terrible policies imposed because of the uranium that France enforces.”²¹.

Most of the negative comments by French users were left on TikTok. Criticisms varied:

- “Macron’s problem is that he confuses the profile of a head of state with that of a newly appointed commercial director in marketing or a startup.”²²
- “And in France, there are plenty of problems. Problems that would actually require the president’s presence”.²³

¹⁹ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ Instagram post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DCmMWLkpD2B/> on March 10, 2025.

²⁰ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ Instagram post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/DCmMWLkpD2B/> on March 10, 2025.

²¹ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631 on March 10, 2025.

²² Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631 on March 10, 2025.

²³ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631 on March 10, 2025.

- “Aren’t there other topics besides croissants?”²⁴
- “Mr. Macron, while you’re busy making friends abroad, your country is in terrible shape... Anyway, good luck with your efforts...”²⁵
- “What kind of question is this? Seriously, am I dreaming? What world am I in?”²⁶

4.5.2.5 Sentiment analysis results

The sentiment analysis of Paul Cabannes’ collaborative posts with French diplomatic institutions highlights key patterns in audience reactions.

Figure 15 - Sentiment analysis across all posts on Instagram and TikTok

Note. Chart created by the author on March 22, 2025.

²⁴ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631 on March 10, 2025.

²⁵ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631 on March 10, 2025.

²⁶ Comment posted by a user under Paul Cabannes’ TikTok post, “Thank you @elysee” published on November 20, 2024. Retrieved from https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631 on March 10, 2025.

1. High positive sentiment for humour-driven cultural content

Posts received high positive reactions from readers when humor related to cultural topics, especially when comparing French and Brazilian elements (Posts 1–3). However, the fourth post received the highest positive sentiment score reaching 83.52% on Instagram and 69.78% on TikTok, due to its association with President Macron. TikTok users found Post 3 amusing because of its language-related jokes which resulted in 64.44% positive sentiment.

Numerous comments contained happy and admiring statements along with personal anecdotes. Post 1 contains a heartwarming account from a user whose daughter progressed from French learning to French residence and studies. Users provided cultural insights through their posts including an extensive historical account of the Dunkirk Carnival which demonstrated that humour-based diplomacy can serve educational purposes.

2. Neutral sentiment based on curiosity and cultural conversation

The neutral category included factual statements together with personal thoughts and questions which emerged from watching the videos. Users in Post 1 (38.14% on IG; 26% on TT) and 2 (37.43% on IG; 43.85% on TT) particularly demonstrated personal biases about the comparisons on French and Brazilian cultural representation (i.e. Neymar vs Mbappé) and continued the discussion in the comments. Post 3 also accounted for a high number of neutral comments (41.84% on IG; 32.78% on TT), mostly with non-opinionated comments, questions and factual statements. In Post 4, rates of neutral comments were significantly lower than other posts (12.66% on IG; 15.65 on TT) and displayed interest in the French audience's reaction by asking if they found the humour relatable which demonstrated the possibility of cross-cultural dialogue through neutral comments.

3. Political topics were met with mixed feelings and more negative reactions

The most negative comments were found in Post 4, especially on TikTok (14.57% negative sentiment, compared to 3.83% on Instagram). Many negative comments were not related to the video itself, but to other political issues, such as the boycott of Brazilian meat by Carrefour in France or France's colonial past. Post 1 also triggered political discussion, with one comment referring to French lobbying efforts to remove Spanish as a required subject in Brazilian high schools. These examples show that even light or humorous diplomatic content can lead to serious political discussions.

4. Negative stereotypes and cultural biases were present in small percentages

Three out of four posts received minor negative comments, yet it has been observed that some users expressed stereotypes and prejudices. Users in Post 3 made jokes that included statements like "*Nobody showers there*" and called French people arrogant. The few existing biased statements demonstrate how cultural prejudices affect public perception thus requiring digital diplomacy to actively monitor these narratives.

5. Intense response to personal experiences and sharing of memories

Users across all posts add personal anecdotes which included expressing the desire of learning French, as well as traveling to France and their emotional connections with the country. The comments indicate that this content extends past entertainment purposes to create a space where audiences can reflect about their cultural identity and personal experiences. Multiple users in Post 1 expressed gratitude and pride about connecting with French culture which demonstrates how relatable content strengthens emotional diplomatic power.

The sentiment analysis shows that the audience has a high level of interaction with humour-based diplomatic content, with the most positive reactions related to cultural and linguistic themes. Neutral comments were often based on curiosity and factual knowledge, while negative reactions were mostly related to external political issues and not to the content

itself. In conclusion, the findings of this study support the idea that influencer-led diplomacy not only increases engagement but also requires careful navigation of the diverse reactions of the audience. Thus, by tracking sentiment trends, diplomatic institutions can refine their digital strategies to make sure that their messages are heard across cultural and political divides.

4.5 Comparative analysis: Instagram vs. TikTok

In this chapter we compared TikTok and Instagram to explore variations in engagement and sentiment stemming from the use of influencers in digital public diplomacy. By analysing Paul Cabannes' collaborations with French diplomatic institutions, the analysis looked at how different digital audiences respond to diplomatic messaging, humour, and political content across these two online platforms.

Our engagement analysis reveals distinct interaction patterns between TikTok and Instagram. Starting with Instagram, it is observed that the platform generates more active engagement (comments) than TikTok. For Post 4, Instagram received 11,500 comments compared to TikTok's 4,600, highlighting Instagram's effectiveness at sparking text-based discussions. In terms of sentiment, overall positive comments were identified, followed by neutral and negative ones, across all posts.

Figure 16 - Sentiment across Instagram

Note. Chart created by the author on March 22, 2025.

The fourth post featuring President Emmanuel Macron received the most significant number of positive comments (83.52%), followed by the second (59.19%), first (54.14%) and third (52.37%) posts. These level of praise of posts 1, 2 and 3 are balanced, with only post 2 receiving a slightly higher favour. Similarly, this trend can be observed when it comes to neutral comments, which did not necessarily expressed either positive or negative reactions, with posts 1 to 3 ranging from 37.43% (post 2) to 41.84% (post 3). With only 12.66%, Post 4 showed the lower rates of neutral comments out of all four. In terms of negative reactions, Post 1 leads the ranking with 7.72%, most of them accounting for disagreements about the options available for Cabannes to choose from, regarding Brazilian representation.

On the other hand, TikTok generally receives more passive engagement (likes) than Instagram, particularly across posts 1, 2, and 4, demonstrating its strength in quickly accumulating reactions. Sentiment analysis reveals TikTok has more positive comments than

Instagram, led by Post 1 (71%) and followed by Post 4 (69.78%), Post 3 (64.44%) and Post 2 (48.85%).

Figure 17 - Sentiment across TikTok

Note. Chart created by the author on March 22, 2025.

The dataset demonstrates TikTok audiences had a strong positive response to funny and light content, especially in Post 1, where bilateral relations and personal preferences were themed, and 71% of the comments were positive. For instance, TikTok users responded with humorous remarks, while Instagram users shared detailed insights, such as information about the Dunkirk Carnival. This can be attributed to TikTok's algorithm prioritizing viral content based on high-intensity interactions such as likes and views. On the contrary, the comment section of Instagram for Post 1 encourages the community to engage in the discussion, making it more suitable for diplomatic conversations.

Post 4 also received a high level of praise, accounting for 69.78% of positive comments, although significantly lower than Instagram's rate (83.52%). In further contrast with Instagram,

neutral comments varied greatly, ranging from 15.65% on Post 4 to 43.85% on Post 2. TikTok had the most negative comments in Post 4, mainly from French commenters criticizing Macron's policies or Brazilians protesting against Carrefour policies, whereas Instagram users were more focused on Cabannes and his success in meeting the President. This shows that funny and lightweight content is well received by almost everyone, whereas political content leads to a higher level of polarization, especially on TikTok.

Based on the data available, Instagram encourages more active participation than TikTok. On Instagram, users generally post longer comments, argue, and comment with questions and answers, whereas TikTok comments tend to be brief, spontaneous, and meme-like. Instagram's higher proportion of neutral comments suggests users are more likely to comment and discuss, fostering discussions about cultural and diplomatic topics. For example, in Post 1, Dunkirk Carnival is explained in historical context by Instagram users, while TikTok comments were mostly short reaction words.

Conversely, negative sentiment remains low on both platforms, except for Post 4, where TikTok had the highest percentage of negative comments (14.57%). Therefore, a higher percentage of negative comments is observed in politically-oriented content (Post 4 – Macron's video). For Instagram, the rate of confrontational politically-oriented comments is less present, resulting in more praised or discussion-oriented comments than critical ones.

All in all, this comparative analysis has revealed the differences in audience behaviour between the two platforms, Instagram and TikTok, in the context of digital public diplomacy. To sum up, TikTok is a better platform for diplomatic humor and is highly likely to go viral, but the audience is more likely to react than engage in meaningful discussion. Instagram is structured in a way that enables it to facilitate interactive public diplomacy and detailed discussions. By contrast, TikTok is more political than Instagram and thus results in more

negative engagement. Both platforms have their strengths in humorous content, but TikTok has a more positive signal than Instagram.

These findings further support the notion that platform-specific strategies are required for digital diplomacy. Even though TikTok is good at generating soft power through virality, Instagram is crucial for moderate and meaningful diplomatic conversations. Understanding these dynamics can help refine strategies for influencer-led diplomatic engagement in the digital age.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

Public diplomacy has evolved in the context of a *network society* (Castells, 2009), leading to the rise to *people-to-people* diplomatic approaches (Snow, 2009) and *new public diplomacy* (Melissen, 2005). This new public diplomacy is categorized by a growing recognition of the impact of listening and non-state actors in public diplomacy, as well as a focus on relationship-building practices. Complementary, the advance of digital spaces provoked a digitalization process of public diplomacy (Manor, 2019), in which public diplomats have to continuously adapt to seek effectiveness.

Even before the advent of digital technologies, the rise of networked communications fostered policymakers and public diplomats to try to manage public opinion. For these purposes, mass media outlets were their preferred mediums of messaging transmission. Within this context, Lazarsfeld et. al (1948) proposed a *two-step communication flow model* to assess other actors who influenced opinions besides media outlets. In this model, they identified *opinion leaders*, individuals who act as intermediaries, interpreting messages from the media and passing onto others.

In the digital age, Lazarsfeld's concept of opinion leaders can be translated with the modern status of social media influencers (SMIs). These influencers are content creators and internet personalities who benefit from the opportunities of *digital participation* (Reed, 2009). As content creators, SMIs can range from experts in certain fields serving educational purposes or focused on relatability and humour to engage with their followers, resulting in a process where they build and nurture their digital communities continuously on one or across multiple platforms. In a way, they are deemed as a new type of celebrities who do not depend on traditional media outlets to build reach and engagement. Due to their increasing online visibility, organizations seek to develop partnerships with SMIs to reach new audiences.

This thesis examined how SMIs act as non-state actors and opinion leaders in public diplomacy, focusing on the case of Paul Cabannes and his collaborations with French diplomatic institutions in Brazil. As a Frenchman living in Brazil for nearly a decade, Cabannes is considered both a local non-state actor and a diaspora stakeholder for the French mission in Brazil. His usual content is satirical, humorous, and explores the cultural differences between the two countries. Over the course of seven months (April to November 2024), Cabannes officially collaborated four times with French diplomatic institutions on social media, especially with the French Embassy in Brasília. He also seems to be intrinsically connected to the French-Brazil cultural network, as we can observe through Putnoki's Instagram posts, the South America Director of ATOU France. His presence in the 2024 French Cinema Varilux Festival in São Paulo reveals his contributions as a non-state actor in France's public diplomacy in Brazil go beyond the digital sphere.

Lee and Ayhan (2015) argue that local non-state actors often enjoy more credibility with audiences, as they do not tend to follow political agendas. Moreover, Zaharna (2014) also shares this opinion by highlighting the advantages of nonpolitical networks, as well as *network bridges*, to build trust and achieve long-term goals. Going further into networked public diplomacy strategies, Zaharna (2014) addresses the definitions of network density and centrality, advocating that denser networks are often well-connected and more prone to sharing ideas, values and behaviours. As for centrality, Zaharna (2014) suggests that a smaller number of focal actors in a network and, therefore, a more centralized network, can be a bit more restricted but better to achieve simpler tasks.

Paul Cabannes – as a nonpolitical actor who is part of French's culture, values and identity – is an excellent example of an individual that can function as a bridge between cultures of two different foreign publics. When we analyse the network of actors behind the case study's digital collaborations, it is clear not many actors seem to be involved. In total, four institutions

are present: the French Embassy in Brasília, the French Consulate in São Paulo, and the French Consulate in Rio de Janeiro. A cross-institutional partnership is also observed: in the second post, the Brazilian Embassy in France also collaborated on Instagram with the French Embassy and Cabannes. The limited number of actors demonstrates this network is rather denser than sparser, and the focal presence of the French Embassy in Brasília across all collaborations displays a high level of centrality, with the embassy assuming their organization.

On another note, Lee and Ayhan (2015) further explore the concepts of network centrality, offering insights on *in-* and *out-degree centrality*. For the case of Cabannes's partnerships with French diplomatic institutions, the impact of Cabannes's in-degree centrality as an SMIs with his own network merits investigation. His visibility and follower count on both analysed social media platforms consists of 2.3 million followers on Instagram and 2.4 million followers on TikTok, summing up to 4.5 million followers, a robust network and community.

As a result of collaborating with Cabannes, the four posts analysed demonstrated a notable increase in engagement on both platforms. French diplomatic institutions in Brazil show overall low engagement on social media, with most posts receiving fewer than 4K likes and less than 300 comments. All four influencer posts exceeded French engagement averages on Instagram. Post 3 (with the French Consulate in São Paulo) received 69.5K likes, 6x higher than the top-performing consular post (Rio de Janeiro, 4.2K likes). Post 2 (shared by French and Brazilian embassies) got 67.3K likes, higher than usual embassy posts. Post 4 (featuring President Macron) received 477.7K likes and 16.1K comments, with an increase of 16,000% compared to typical embassy engagement. Even the least-engaged post had over 69K likes, 20x more than the French Embassy's Instagram average.

Metrics on passive (likes) and active (comments) engagement testify the high levels of social media usage in Brazil (Statista, 2025). Considering this cultural trait, France's decision

to engage with Brazilian publics on social media through influencer-led collaborations correlates with Manor's (2019) understanding of *tailored communication*, which prompts public diplomats to create content bearing in mind the specific needs of their targeted audiences. By investing in digitalized public diplomacy in collaboration with Cabannes, a prominent online figure while adopting a light-hearted tone, France's mission in Brazil is employing tailored communication strategies that resonates with a highly digital-driven audience.

When analysing the themes and messaging of the posts, we can observe a clear trend towards the promotion of culture and values, consistent with soft power strategies (Nye, 2004). All four posts emphasize France-Brazil cultural exchange, each varying in tone and level of government involvement. Humor and satire are used to transmit diplomatic themes in an accessible and engaging manner.

The first post ("France vs Brazil"), published on April 29, 2022, centred around cultural identity and preferences, under a form of "formal satire", in which Cabannes is frames between both national flags and engages in Q&A about choosing between French and Brazilian culture. Post 2 ("A beautiful partnership"), published on August 16, 2024, themed mostly on bilateral relations and sports rivalry. The style is similar to first one, but it follows a "debate format" between both embassies which are directly involved. Post 3 ("That's crazy"), published on November 9, 2024, is the most informal, under a bar setting showing a playful discussion about French-origin words in Portuguese. Language and culinary exchange are the main topics, with a humorous and educational undertone. This is also the only post where diplomatic representatives are not directly involved in the video, encouraging organic engagement through cultural curiosity, avoiding a promotional tone. Finally, Post 4 ("Thank you to @Elysee"), published on November 20, 2024, features Emmanuel Macron. The video depicts French diplomacy and soft power, under a formal satire format with direct political presence. It also

merges light humor with formal diplomacy, showing how political figures can adapt to digital formats.

The findings of the sentiment analysis match Cull's (2019) concept of *social listening* in digital diplomacy, which states that diplomatic actors must take advantage of social media platforms to listen to audiences. Cabannes' collaborative posts contained a high load of comments, which can be used to guide diplomatic practices. Overall, posts received a high positive sentiment, especially for humor-based, culturally themed posts. Post 4 (with President Macron) got the highest positivity (83.52% IG; 69.78% TT) and Post 3 (based on language humour) was also well-received (64.44% TT; 52.37% IG).

Neutral comments reflected curiosity, cultural facts, and personal experiences, extending the conversation (e.g., Neymar vs. Mbappé, Dunkirk Carnival). Many users shared personal stories, showing emotional and cultural connections with France, thus reinforcing soft power through relatability. Negative sentiment was low overall, but Post 4 obtained more criticism, especially on TikTok, due to political issues (e.g., meat boycott, colonialism, disagreement with Macron's policies). This shows that political content, particularly if it involves state figures, needs more careful planning to avoid controversy. Some cultural stereotypes were observed (e.g., French hygiene jokes), though in small numbers.

While the insights drawn from the sentiment analysis are proven to be meaningful in the context of social listening in digitalized public diplomacy, Cull (2019) cautions that listening practices must be active and systematic to be effective. Therefore, similarly to the Sweden Institute's case, the French mission in Brazil must keep count of sentiments in all their digital diplomacy strategies, influencer-led or not. As Di Martino (2020) maintains, a public diplomat aware of online opinions will be prepared to engage with them.

Another reflection regarding this case study's sentiment analysis involves Grunig and Hunt's (1984) two-way symmetrical communication model. When suggesting an excellent

model for PR, which can be translated into public diplomacy practices, Grunig and Hunt (1984) propose that communicators must strive to promote true dialogue aiming at achieving mutual collaboration (the two-way symmetrical model). The lack of responses to social media comments from both Cabannes and French institutions suggests that, although encouraging participation on posts, the network is losing opportunities to engage in meaningful conversations and to build actual relationships with the audience. Therefore, these collaborations exhibit the presence of a *two-way asymmetrical model*, which uses feedback persuade, aiming to mostly benefit the organization over the public.

Zaharna (2009)'s relational framework also highlights the significance of dialogue, trust, and long-term goals in relationship-building, particularly through second-tier initiatives. These second-tier strategies are characterized by involving multiple actors enjoying of shared coordination of open-ended projects, and a mixed political and nonpolitical nature. As demonstrated, the lack of dialogue in the comment section does not configure a weakness for influencer-led strategies, but for all digital diplomacy efforts. Nonetheless, they are still a good example of second-tier relationship-building strategies, since the focus is not to inform or merely persuade, but rather to address highly sensitive cultural topics, while partnering up and establishing a meaningful relationship with a nonpolitical actor.

As the final stage of the empirical analysis, the comparison between Instagram and TikTok offers valuable insights for public diplomacy practitioners. On one hand, Instagram generates more active engagement (e.g., comments), it has more potential for promotion of dialogue and detailed discussions, particularly since Instagram comments are often longer and more thoughtful (e.g., Dunkirk Carnival history). On the other hand, TikTok prioritizes viral content and promotes more passive engagement (likes), especially for humorous posts. Overall, Instagram proves better for diplomatic conversations, while TikTok excels in soft power and reach through light, viral content.

In France's mission in Brazil case, maintaining a strong presence on Instagram is essential, while opportunities to promote a continuous process of social listening (Cull, 2019) and the development of two-way symmetrical communication (Grunig & Hunt, 1984) through comment responses, would prove relevant to improve effectiveness. Implementation of TikTok-focused strategies, however, including the adoption of official accounts, must be further studied to ensure it meets the goals of French's public diplomacy policies. Even if not the best suited platform to raise dialogical public diplomacy strategies, the high level of virality of the platform could prove beneficial for image promotion and persuasion.

The case study of Paul Cabannes' influencer-led collaborations with French diplomatic institutions in Brazil demonstrates how SMIs contribute to modern public diplomacy. Through their position as trustworthy and culturally-aware opinion leaders and non-state actors, SMIs such as Cabannes allow diplomatic missions to establish connections with foreign audiences that traditional digital public diplomacy methods may not achieve. Through his use of humour, cultural curiosity, and authenticity, Cabannes creates connections between institutional messages and audience expectations to generate engagement, visibility, and emotional resonance.

The complete potential of influencer-led diplomacy can be only achieved when combined with sustained relationship development and strategic dialogue practices. The study indicates that strong public engagement with positive sentiment could not lead to enduring diplomatic results if one-way communication persists. The failure to respond to user comments presents an opportunity to build stronger connections while showing genuine interest in public feedback. French digital diplomacy in Brazil needs to move toward dialogical and participatory practices that reflect relational public diplomacy principles to advance from symbolic to substantive engagement.

These collaborations succeed when they generate sustained relationships based on trust, mutual understanding, and shared cultural narratives, in addition to their ability to capture the public's interest. Digitalized public diplomacy strategies will truly benefit from partnerships with social media influencers if supported by listening, responsiveness, and a clear strategic vision tailored to each platform's dynamics.

References

- 20 Minutes. (2024, July 22). Paul Cabannes casse les stéréotypes culturels entre la France et le Brésil. *20 Minutes*. <https://www.20minutes.fr/arts-stars/culture/paul-cabannes-casse-les-stereotypes-culturels-entre-la-france-et-le-bresil-4567890> (last access: 22 March, 2025)
- ABC Reporter. (2025, January 10). Paul Cabannes leva seu stand-up para Lisboa e Paris. *ABC Reporter*. <https://www.abcreporter.com.br/entretenimento/paul-cabannes-leva-seu-stand-up-para-lisboa-e-paris-2345678> (last access: 22 March, 2025)
- Abidin, C. (2018). Internet celebrity: Understanding fame online. Bingley, England: *Emerald Publishing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/9781787560765>
- Abidin, C. (2021). Mapping internet celebrity on TikTok: Exploring attention economies and visibility labours. Perth, Australia: *Cultural Science Journal*, 12(1), 77–104. <https://doi.org/10.5334/csci.140>
- Agence pour l'Enseignement Français à l'Étranger. (2024). Les établissements homologués au Brésil. <https://www.aefe.fr/pays/ameriques/bresil> (last access: 19 March, 2025)
- Alliance Française. (2024). Réseau des Alliances Françaises au Brésil. <https://www.alliancefr.org/bresil> (last access: 17 March, 2025)
- Araújo, B. C., & Milani, C. R. S. (2011). *Brazil's South–South cooperation strategies: From foreign policy to public policy*. In S. Chaturvedi, T. Fues, & E. Sidiropoulos (Eds.), *Development cooperation and emerging powers: New partners or old patterns?* (pp. 165–185). London, England: Zed Books.
- Babla, M. (n.d.). Social media and public diplomacy. USC Center on Public Diplomacy. https://uscpublicdiplomacy.org/pdin_monitor_article/social-media-and-public-diplomacy (last access: 15 March, 2025)

- Baum, M. A., & Potter, P. B. K. (2015). *War and democratic constraint: How the public influences foreign policy*. Princeton, NJ: *Princeton University Press*.
<https://www.perlego.com/book/738042>
- BBC News Brasil. (2024, July 29). Carrefour boicota carne brasileira e depois pede desculpas: entenda a polêmica. *BBC News Brasil*. <https://www.bbc.com/portuguese/articles/ced97dz6gq4o> (last access: 17 March, 2025)
- Behnke, E. (2024, July 9). Câmara aprova novo ensino médio sem espanhol obrigatório; texto vai à sanção. *CNN Brasil*. <https://www.cnnbrasil.com.br/politica/camara-aprova-novo-ensino-medio-sem-espanhol-obrigatorio-texto-vai-a-sancao/> (last access: 22 March, 2025)
- Bjola, C., & Holmes, M. (Eds.). (2015). *Digital diplomacy: Theory and practice*. London, England: Routledge. <https://www.perlego.com/book/1561318>
- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, April 29). France vs. Brazil [Instagram post]. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6W6WpUp7C5/>
- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, April 29). France vs. Brazil [TikTok video]. https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7363331028628294918
- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, August 16). After all, it's a beautiful partnership [Instagram post]. https://www.instagram.com/p/C-u_SzcJl7h/
- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, August 16). After all, it's a beautiful partnership [TikTok video]. https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7403521184366742789
- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, November 20). Thank you to @Elysee [Instagram post]. <https://www.instagram.com/p/DCmMWLkpD2B/>
- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, November 20). Thank you to @Elysee [TikTok video]. https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631

- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, November 7). That's crazy [Instagram post].
<https://www.instagram.com/p/DCJ6TcepkhJ/>
- Cabannes, P. [@paulcabannes_]. (2024, November 7). That's crazy [TikTok video].
https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7434548949647641912
- Calmon, M. (2023). Sucesso na web, humorista francês Paul Cabannes se apresenta na Bahia. *A TARDE*. <https://atarde.com.br/cultura/culturateatro/sucesso-na-web-humorista-frances-paul-cabannes-se-apresenta-na-bahia-1221702>.
- Carrillat, F. A., & Ilicic, J. (2019). The celebrity capital life cycle: A framework for future research directions on celebrity endorsement. Abingdon, England: *Journal of Advertising*, 48(1), 61–71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2019.1579689>
- Castells, M. (2009). *Communication power*. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Cooper, A. F. (2008). *Celebrity diplomacy*. Boulder, CO: Paradigm Publishers.
- Cronin, A. K. (2013). How global communications are changing the character of war. *The Whitehead Journal of Diplomacy and International Relations*, 14*(1), 25–39. South Orange, NJ: Seton Hall University. https://ciaotest.cc.columbia.edu/journals/shjdir/v14i1/f_0028740_23334.pdf
- Cull, N. J. (2019). *Public diplomacy: Foundations for global engagement in the digital age*. Cambridge, England: Polity Press.
- Cull, N. J. (2020). Public diplomacy before Gullion: The evolution of a phrase. In N. Snow & N. J. Cull (Eds.), *Routledge Handbook of Public Diplomacy* (2nd ed., pp. 13-17). New York, NY: Routledge. <https://www.perlego.com/book/1595656>
- Cull, Nicholas J. (2009). Public diplomacy: lessons from the past. Los Angeles, California: University of Southern California. Annenberg School for Communication and Journalism. *Center on Public Diplomacy* (CPD Perspectives on public policy, 2009, paper 2), 2009.
- Danzek, L. (2023, March 28). The first TikTok war: Lessons in diplomacy from TikTokers on the frontlines. Durham, England: *Global Policy Journal*.

<https://www.globalpolicyjournal.com/blog/28/03/2023/first-tiktok-war-lessons-diplomacy-tiktokkers-frontlines>

Delage, S. (2024, November 21). Le croissant garni, une hérésie? Cet humoriste français s'incruste au G20 et cuisine Emmanuel Macron. *Ouest-France*. <https://www.ouest-france.fr/leditiondusoir/2024-11-21/le-croissant-garni-une-heresie-cet-humoriste-francais-s-incruste-au-g20-et-cuisine-emmanuel-macron-6b5bbba5-78ef-4c75-b71c-1beadf183ccc>

Deutsche Welle. (2024, July 29). Ensino de espanhol vira batalha de interesses no Brasil. *CartaCapital*. <https://www.cartacapital.com.br/educacao/ensino-de-espanhol-vira-batalha-de-interesses-no-brasil/> (last access: 22 March, 2025)

Di Martino, L. (2020). Conceptualising public diplomacy listening on social media. *Place Branding And Public Diplomacy*, 16(2), 131-142. Basingstoke, England: Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41254-019-00135-5>

Embassy of Germany in Brazil. (n.d.). Instagram profile. <https://www.instagram.com/alemanhanobrasil>

Embassy of Japan in Brazil. (n.d.). Instagram profile. <https://www.instagram.com/embaixadajapao>

Embassy of the United States in Brazil. (n.d.). Instagram profile. <https://www.instagram.com/embaixadaUSA>

Eysink, S. (2005). The Interaction between State and Non-State Actors: The Role of Human Rights within the ASEM Dialogue. *IIASA Interim Report*. IIASA, Laxenburg, Austria: IR-05-044

Floyd, P. B. (2007, November 19). Try policy instead of PR. *Los Angeles Times*, A21. <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-2007-nov-19-oe-floyd19-story.html>.

Fraissat, Z. (Photographer). (2023). Paul Cabannes, que tem milhões de seguidores no TikTok e Instagram [Photograph]. *Folhapress*. <https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/folhateen/2023/05/paul-cabannes-odeia-audios-e-croissant-recheado-mas-adora-o-brasil-e-o-sucesso-que-faz-aqui.shtml>.

- Franco, M. (2023, May 23). Paul Cabannes odeia áudios e croissant recheado, mas adora o Brasil e o sucesso que faz aqui. *Folha de S.Paulo*.
<https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/folhateen/2023/05/paul-cabannes-odeia-audios-e-croissant-recheado-mas-adora-o-brasil-e-o-sucesso-que-faz-aqui.shtml>
- Golan, G. J., & Yang, S.-U. (2014). Introduction: The integrated public diplomacy perspective. In G. J. Golan, S.-U. Yang, & D. F. Kinsey (Eds.), *International public relations and public diplomacy: Communication and engagement* (pp. 1–14). New York, NY: Peter Lang.
<https://www.perlego.com/book/1993832>
- Grundel, I., & Stenberg, J. (2019, March 26). Social listening as a tool for public diplomacy organizations. Los Angeles, CA: *USC Public Diplomacy*.
<https://uscpublicdiplomacy.org/blog/social-listening-tool-public-diplomacy-organizations>
- Grunig, J. E. (2013). Excellence in public relations and communication management: A review of the theory and results. In E. L. Toth (Ed.), *The future of excellence in public relations and communication management: Challenges for the next generation* (pp. 159–178). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Grunig, J. E., & Grunig, L. A. (1992). Models of public relations and communication. In J. E. Grunig (Ed.), *Excellence in public relations and communication management* (pp. 285–325). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Grunig, J. E., & Hunt, T. (1984). *Managing public relations*. New York, NY: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.
- Hucker, J. (2020). *Public opinion and diplomacy: The evolving relationship between policymakers and the public*. Abingdon, England: Routledge.
- Huijgh, E. (2016). *The Public Diplomacy Reader*. Leiden, Netherlands: Brill.
- Ingenhoff, D., Calamai, A., & Sevin, E. (2021). *Public diplomacy and public relations: Intersections, overlaps, and challenges*. Abingdon, England: Routledge.

- Katz, E., & Lazarsfeld, P. F. (1955). *Personal influence: The part played by people in the flow of mass communications*. Glencoe, IL: Free Press.
- Kellner, D. (2010). Celebrity diplomacy, spectacle and Barack Obama. *Celebrity Studies*, 1(1), 121–123. Abingdon, England: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19392390903519156>
- Khamis, S., Ang, L., & Welling, R. (2021). How social media influencers acquire celebrity capital. *Journal of Advertising*, 50(5), 477-492. Abingdon, England: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2021.1977737>
- Lazarsfeld, P. F., Berelson, B., & Gaudet, H. (1948). *The people's choice: How the voter makes up his mind in a presidential campaign (2nd ed.)*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.
- Le Parisien. (2024, August 2). Paul Cabannes, l'humoriste français star au Brésil... et inconnu à Paris [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NbM09k7YePU>
- Lee, G., & Ayhan, K. (2015). Why do we need non-state actors in public diplomacy? Theoretical discussions of relational, networked and collaborative public diplomacy. *Journal of International and Area Studies*, 22(1), 57–77. Seoul, South Korea: Center for International and Area Studies, Hankuk University of Foreign Studies.
- Liu, S. B. (2012). Trending now: Uses of social media for public diplomacy. *The Journal of Public Diplomacy*, 3(2), 1–20. Syracuse, NY: Syracuse University, Public Diplomacy Program.
- Manor, I. (2019). *The digitalization of public diplomacy*. Cham, Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan. <https://www.perlego.com/book/3491230>
- Macron, E. [@emmanuelmacron]. (2024, November 20). I'm sure we'll find an agreement on the croissant. [Comment on the video "Thank you to @Elysee"]. TikTok. https://www.tiktok.com/@paulcabannes_/video/7439372621596216631.
- Martino, L. M. S. (2018). Reading 'The People's Choice' in its 70th anniversary: From 'opinion leaders' to 'digital influencers'. *Comunicação & Sociedade*, 39(31), 29–44. São Paulo, Brazil:

Intercom – Sociedade Brasileira de Estudos Interdisciplinares da Comunicação.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-5844201831>.

Melissen, J. (Ed.). (2005). *The new public diplomacy: Soft power in international relations*. Basingstoke, England: Palgrave Macmillan.
https://culturaldiplomacy.org/academy/pdf/research/books/soft_power/.

Ministère de la Culture. (2024). Les relations littéraires franco-brésiliennes.
<https://www.culture.gouv.fr/Actualites/Les-relations-litteraires-franco-bresiliennes>

Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires étrangères. (n.d.). The work of the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs. *France Diplomatie*. from <https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/en/the-ministry-and-its-network/the-work-of-the-ministry-for-europe-and-foreign-affairs/>.

Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs. (2022). *Digital soft diplomacy*. French Government.
<https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/en/french-foreign-policy/digital-diplomacy/digital-soft-diplomacy/>

Nye, J. S. (2004). *Soft power: The means to success in world politics*. New York, NY: PublicAffairs.

Oliveira, M. (2010). Ano da França no Brasil: Um balanço das relações culturais franco-brasileiras. *Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional*, 53(2), 123–140. Brasília, Brazil: Instituto Brasileiro de Relações Internacionais.

Olmastroni, F. (2014). *Framing War* (1st ed.). Abingdon, England: Routledge.
<https://www.perlego.com/book/716780>

Ouest-France. (2024, March 5). Paul Cabannes: Un humoriste français qui rapproche la France et le Brésil. *Ouest-France*. <https://www.ouest-france.fr/culture/paul-cabannes-un-humoriste-francais-qui-rapproche-la-france-et-le-bresil-3456789>

- Pamment, J. (2015). Digital diplomacy as transmedia engagement: Aligning theories of participatory culture with international advocacy campaigns. *New Media & Society*, 18(9), 2046–2062. London, England: SAGE Publications. <https://portal.research.lu.se/en/publications/digital-diplomacy-as-transmedia-engagement-aligning-theories-of-p>.
- Perla, H. Jr. (2011). Explaining public support for the use of military force: The impact of reference point framing and prospective decision making. *International Organization*, 65(1), 139–167. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23016106>.
- Putnoki, C. [@carolineputnokioficial]. (2024, November 6). No Festival Varilux, @variluxcinefrances uns papos animados moderados pela...[Instagram post]. <https://www.instagram.com/p/DAUMmkKSABC/>.
- Putnoki, C. [@carolineputnokioficial]. (2024, September 24). Encontrei no Consulado Geral, na semana passada, com os dois Franceses FR mais conhecidos...[Instagram post]. <https://www.instagram.com/p/DAUMmkKSABC/>.
- Reed, M. (2019). The role of social media in contemporary public diplomacy: A critical assessment. *Journal of Public Diplomacy*, 4(1), 45–62. Seoul, South Korea: Ewha Womans University.
- Scheule, T. (2024, February 15). Influencer diplomacy. *Diplomatisches Magazin*. Berlin, Germany: Diplomatisches Magazin. <https://www.diplomatisches-magazin.de/en/article/influencer-diplomacy/>
- Seib, P. (2016). *The future of diplomacy*. Cambridge, England: Polity Press.
- Seib, P. (2012). *Real-time diplomacy: Politics and power in the social media era*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan. <https://www.perlego.com/book/3505634>
- Snow, N. (2009). Rethinking public diplomacy. In N. Snow & P. M. Taylor (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of public diplomacy* (pp. 3–11). New York, NY: Routledge.

- Statista. (2025, February 11). *Social media usage in Brazil – Statistics & facts*.
<https://www.statista.com/topics/6949/social-media-usage-in-brazil/#topicOverview>.
- Statista. (2025, January 30). *Brazil: Social media usage rate 2017–2024*.
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1083556/brazil-social-media-usage-rate/>.
- Steger, Manfred B. (2003). *Globalization: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Storie, L., & Marschlich, S. (2023). Listening across borders: Global considerations for listening and public diplomacy. In K. Place (Ed.), *Organizational listening for strategic communication* (pp. xxx–xxx). Abingdon, England: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003273851-20>
- Su, C. (2024, November 13). Be my guest: How Taiwan is using social media influencers for international engagement. *Taiwan Insight*. Nottingham, England: University of Nottingham Asia Research Institute. <https://taiwaninsight.org/2024/11/13/be-my-guest-how-taiwan-is-using-social-media-influencers-for-international-engagement/>.
- Szondi, G. (2009). Central and Eastern European public diplomacy: A transitional perspective on national reputation management. In N. Snow & P. M. Taylor (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of public diplomacy* (pp. 292–313). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Taylor, P. (2002). *Global Communications, International Affairs and the Media Since 1945 (1st ed.)*. Abingdon, England: Routledge. <https://www.perlego.com/book/1620408>.
- UNESCO. (2024). *La France au Brésil: Bibliothèque numérique*. <https://france-bresil.ens-lyon.fr>.
- Weakliem, D. L. (2020). *Public opinion*. Cambridge, England: Polity Press.
- Xu, Y., He, Q., & Ni, S. (2020). Evaluating online public sentiments towards China: A case study of English and Chinese Twitter discourse during the 2019 Chinese National Day. *arXiv*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.04034>.

Zaharna, R. S. (2009). Mapping out a spectrum of public diplomacy initiatives: Information and relational communication frameworks. In N. Snow & P. M. Taylor (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of public diplomacy* (pp. 86–100). New York, NY: Routledge.

Zhang, J., & Pan, S. (2021). Key influencers in public diplomacy 2.0: A country-based social network analysis. *Social Media + Society*, 7(1). London, England: SAGE Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305120981053>